

ESS Instrument Construction Proposal
ESPRESSO

	Name	Affiliation
Main proposer	Malcolm Guthrie	ESS (Sweden)
Co-proposers	Maria Baldini Reini Boehler Craig Bull Paul Henry Stefan Klotz John Loveday Pedro Noguera José Luis Martínez Peña Jesús Pedro de Vicente	Geophysical Laboratory (USA) Geophysical Laboratory (USA) ISIS Facility (UK) ESS (Sweden) UPMC (France) University of Edinburgh (UK) Added Value Solutions S.L. (Spain) ESS Bilbao (Spain) ESS Bilbao (Spain)
Contributors to Science and Technical Case	Mads Bertelsen Leonid Dubrovinsky Natalia Dubrovinskaia Francesca Fabianni Hanns-Peter Liermann Jung-fu Lin Stephen Moggach John Parise Simon Parsons Colin Pulham Phil Salmon Chrysteal Sanloup Stanislav Sinogeikin Andrew Wills Björn Winkler	Danish ESS Simulation Group (Denmark) Universität Bayreuth (Germany) Universität Bayreuth (Germany) Universität Göttingen (Germany) DESY Synchrotron (Germany) University of Texas at Austin (USA) University of Edinburgh (UK) Stonybrook University (USA) University of Edinburgh (UK) University of Edinburgh (UK) University of Edinburgh (UK) University of Bath (UK) UPMC (France) HPCAT beamline, APS (USA) University College London (UK) Frankfurt Universität (Germany)
ESS coordinator	Paul Henry	ESS (Sweden)

Note: All proposals received by ESS will be included as Expressions of Interest for In-kind contributions. ESS will use this information for planning purposes and the proposer or affiliated organization is not obligated to materially contribute to the project. *The following table is used to track the ESS internal distribution of the submitted proposal.*

	Name	Affiliation
Document reviewer	Ken Andersen	ESS (Sweden)
Distribution	Dimitri Argyriou, Oliver Kirstein, Arno Hiess, Robert Connatser, Sindra Petersson Årsköld, Richard Hall-Wilton, Phillip Bentley, Iain Sutton, Thomas Gahl, relevant STAP	

ENCLOSURES

Appendix A: Survey of synchrotron publications
Appendix B: Hydrogen and the dense molecular ices
Appendix C: Superconducting hydrogen rich materials
Appendix D: Low and ambient pressure applications of ESPRESSO
Appendix E: Guide calculations
Appendix F: Attenuation of different cell construction materials
Appendix G: Flux comparison between ESPRESSO, SNAP and PEARL
Appendix H: Pixel size and estimated count-rates
Appendix I: Comparison of ESPRESSO powder data with SNAP
Appendix J: Double aperture calculations
Appendix K: Pressure cell R&D project
Appendix L: Diamond attenuation correction
Appendix M: Budgetary analysis

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

High-pressure science has an incredibly broad scope that, in the last 30 years, has grown to impact fields as diverse as material science, fundamental chemistry, geo and planetary science and even biology. Many of the most fascinating and important phenomena, however, are found at pressures so extreme that they have precluded the critical information available only through neutron-diffraction measurements. The unprecedented brightness at the ESS provides an opportunity to truly revolutionise the field of high-pressure science, which we hope to realise with a dedicated diffractometer called ESPRESSO: the **Extreme Sample PRESSure Spallation Observatory**. This name reflects two defining characteristics of the instrument: firstly, as with the short coffee, ESPRESSO will concentrate the flux of the ESS into a very small, intense beam; Secondly, high pressure is a critical ingredient of the finished product.

The impact from this new instrument will be immediate and sweeping. Successful flagship experiments will exploit neutron diffraction's unparalleled sensitivity to light elements at unprecedented pressures. Initial targets will include the first ever determination of the structure of dense hydrogen and deuterium and reveal the complex details of the quantum interactions between their molecules. Structural measurements of dense ice will provide our first window on pressure-induced quantum tunnelling, molecular dissociation and superionic behaviour in that system. In addition to fundamental science, these processes are believed to play a key role in the interiors of Uranus and Neptune, possibly giving rise to their unusual, and as yet unexplained, magnetic fields.

Another key attribute of neutrons is their unique ability to measure nuclear and magnetic structure simultaneously. ESPRESSO will enable such measurements in completely new regimes of phase space. A clear goal is to realise the intense pressures and temperatures of the outer core of the Earth in order to probe geophysically important phenomena such as high-to-low spin transitions. Not only the extreme pressures, but also the extreme temperatures required to do this are simply not accessible with present-day neutron instrumentation. In addition, and of equal importance, ESPRESSO's potent ability to operate with microscopic samples facilitates a route to *extremely low temperatures* through miniaturisation of pressure cells. The combination of high pressure and temperatures approaching 1K will make ESPRESSO a unique tool for understanding the links between magnetism and superconductivity. The use of pressure, as opposed to doping, to explore systematics in correlated electron systems, especially magnetism, is a nascent field that ESPRESSO will be ideally positioned to catalyse.

These and many other high-profile experiments will alert the vibrant high-pressure communities of Europe to the new (and virtually untapped) potential for neutron science under these previously inaccessible conditions. Not only do these communities provide a well-established user base for

ESPRESSO, but also the success of this beamline will likely stimulate interest in the broader pressure capabilities of European neutron instrumentation. ESS already includes a coherent platform for implementing high pressure across many ESS instruments (within Science Support Systems), but a dedicated instrument is critical to complete the envisaged suite of capabilities. *By delivering the ultimate achievable extremes of pressure and temperature, ESPRESSO will enable the most challenging and groundbreaking science.*

In design, ESPRESSO uses a classic, 90° diffraction geometry employed by the first high-pressure beamline at the Idaho Falls reactor in the 1960's, which is intrinsically optimal for excluding scattering from the sample containment. However, novel elements are found in both its optimisation for micro-beams (<1mm diameter) and its open, accessible sample position. A 'synchrotron-esque' flexibility both facilitating sophisticated collimation and online laser spectroscopy while creating a user-friendly design. In addition, it will benefit from the ESS pulse structure, possessing the ability to optimise for either flux or resolution as the scientific case demands, a versatility not seen in any existing high-pressure neutron diffractometer. A spectral switch will enable access to either thermal or cold segments of the ESS butterfly moderator giving extensive coverage of reciprocal space.

The envisaged detector geometry and collimation will be perfectly harmonised with new classes of diamond-anvil based pressure cells. Indeed, a key aspect of this proposal is the coordinated development of both instrument and sample-environment. Perhaps more so than other instruments, ESPRESSO will depend on dedicated sample environment that must be perfectly matched to the characteristics of the diffractometer. Members of the ESPRESSO team have already developed neutron diamond-anvil cells holding the World pressure record (94 GPa) for measurement of quantitative neutron Bragg intensities. This achievement, at the SNAP diffractometer at the SNS, is a clear proof of principal for ESPRESSO. However, full implementation on SNAP - or any other existing high pressure beamline - is limited by intrinsic instrumentation compromises to enable sample sizes of up to ~1cm. ESPRESSO will realise the full potential of these and next-generation neutron diamond cells.

In summary, we present a clear opportunity to create a fundamental revolution in extreme-conditions neutron science at the ESS. ESPRESSO will provide this transformative capability by permitting neutron crystallographic measurements under entirely new regimes of pressure and temperature.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ENCLOSURES	2
Executive Summary	2
Table of Contents	3
1. Instrument Proposal	4
1.1 <i>Scientific Case</i>	4
1.2 <i>Description of Instrument Concept and Performance</i>	10
1.3 <i>Technical Maturity</i>	22
1.4 <i>In Kind Contributions To Project</i>	23
1.5 <i>Costing</i>	23
2. Bibliography	24
3. List of Abbreviations	28
4. Appendices	28

1. INSTRUMENT PROPOSAL

1.1 SCIENTIFIC CASE

The era of high-pressure (HP) research began in the early 1900's when Percy Bridgman revealed a whole world of new phenomena under gigapascal^a (GPa) pressures (earning the 1946 Nobel Prize in Physics). Arguably a second revolution occurred when intense synchrotron beams were coupled with diamond anvil cells (DACs) in the late 1980's. The dramatic increase in HP science that followed (Table 1) led to the establishment of dedicated beamlines at the majority of synchrotrons^b. However, most synchrotron work occurs above 25 GPa, *territory that is virtually unexplored with neutrons*. Indeed, although a survey of publications (Appendix A) from both the ESRF and APS indicated over 40% would benefit from neutron diffraction data, *the majority could not be realised with existing neutron instrumentation*.

Synchrotron, country	Dedicated HP beamlines	Beamlines	Expt.'s/year	Over-subscription	Avg. pubs/year
ESRF, France	2	ID9A, ID27	~50	~2	66
PETRA-III, Germany	1	P02.2	40-50	~2.5	22
APS, USA	4.5	13-ID-B, 16-BM-B/D, 16-ID-B/E	176 ^d	3.3	105

Table 1 Statistics of high-pressure activity at some European and Worldwide synchrotrons

The success of synchrotron HP science is directly attributable to the symbiosis between microscopic x-ray beams and HP samples. For the first time, the ESS offers the possibility of neutron beams optimised for sub-mm samples. In parallel, recent developments in diamond-anvil cell technology have enabled 100-fold increases in sample volumes¹. Together, this creates an opportunity, that ESPRESSO will realise, for a new generation of HP neutron science, bringing the unique capabilities of neutron diffraction to bear in a vastly expanded phase space (Figure 1).

The rich science enabled by this instrument will be perfectly harmonised with existing synchrotron activity. ESPRESSO's capabilities will immediately stimulate the synchrotron community's interest in neutron science generating a ready-made user-base that may then expand to other neutron instruments.

1.1.1 Light Elements

Solid Hydrogen The first element in the periodic table is one of the most intensively studied under HP. The process by which it becomes metallic and non-molecular and its exotic forms – metallic hydrogen is predicted to be both a liquid superconductor and a superfluid^{3,4} – intrigue theoreticians and experimentalists alike^{5,6}. Hydrogen is a system where nuclear quantum effects (nuclear spin states and zero point motion^{7,8}) play a significant role presenting considerable challenges for theoretical models^{9,10}. In spite of all of this interest, the structures of solid hydrogen and deuterium remain largely unknown and studies of both are necessary to elucidate enormous isotope effects¹¹.

ESPRESSO will provide the first structural measurements of D₂ and H₂ at pressures exceeding 100 GPa. It will reveal the structural basis for a non ideal hard-sphere c/a ratio, reported above 10 GPa¹²,

Figure 1 Coloured areas show P-T access with existing neutron instrumentation. Dashed line shows regime enabled by ESPRESSO (shaded area indicates range with existing sample environment, but clear routes to extend this as discussed in Section 1.2.10)

^a 1 GPa = 10³ atmospheric pressure: the Mariana Trench approaches 0.1 GPa, the core of the Earth is ~350 GPa.

^b At the time of writing these include the ESRF, APS, SPring-8, DLS, PETRA-III and Soleil.

and implying a loss of quantum rotor behaviour. With a highest d-spacing of only 1.65 Å (at 100 GPa), intense thermal neutron flux is critical to study H₂(D₂): At 90°, wavelengths of 0.7 Å or below are needed to probe subtle deviations from perfect spherical symmetry. The quantum-ordering transition at low temperature (T) is also a target: no proposed theoretical structures agree with the only neutron diffraction study, which (with very sparse data) suggested a controversial incommensurate model⁸. Simulated diffraction (Appendix B) shows the key instrumental requirement remains high thermal flux. At greater pressures still, the structure of phase-III, intermediate in the process of full molecular breakdown, is completely unknown and ESPRESSO will provide the first direct information on this.

The molecular ices Water, ammonia and methane are familiar materials that behave exotically at very HP. Pressure induces a progressive breakdown of the molecular state, leading to unusual behaviour like superionicity¹³⁻¹⁵. These ices also provide a "laboratory" to study protons (or deuterons) within a wide range of potentials, yielding insight into their quantum nature with broad impact in diverse fields from complex biological reactions through to the 'mineralogy' of planetary bodies such as Uranus, Neptune and Titan. However, the P range corresponding to molecular dissociation is completely unexplored with neutron diffraction, the only technique sensitive to the location of the H(D) atoms that dominate the composition of these materials.

Each ice has its own set of profound unanswered questions (Appendix B). Key goals are characterising H-bond centring in water ice (and settling recent, controversial claims of an interstitial phase¹⁶), the nature of superionicity in both water and ammonia, and the balance between polymerisation and dissociation in methane. ESPRESSO will provide a new window on such light-atom structure in the 100 GPa regime. This science makes stringent demands on the instrument, which must pivot between competing needs for flux and resolution across a wide range of Q space. In the case of HP ice, distinguishing between quantum tunnelling and H-bond centring demands measurements of Bragg reflections down to at least 0.5 Å in d-spacing. Meanwhile, the crystallography of representative structures, such as methane A (see Appendix B), illustrates the need for wavelengths approaching 8 Å to access the high d-spacing reflections, invaluable for indexing new phases. Simultaneously, $\delta d/d$ resolution of better than 0.6% is required to resolve overlapping powder peaks.

Superconducting H-rich systems The (as yet unreachable) pressures required to metallise H₂ have driven a search for alternative routes to reach this exotic state. In 2005, Neil Ashcroft proposed this might be achieved by using covalent bonds to pull hydrogen atoms into close proximity¹⁷. This suggestion triggered an avalanche of theoretical and experimental work¹⁸⁻²⁷ on the group 14 hydrides (silane etc.), solvated electron systems like Li:NH₃, and hydrides of the alkali and alkaline earth elements (KH₈, NaH₈ etc.). The diverse structural phenomena uncovered have been studied with theory, spectroscopy and x-rays, but structural detail on the H(D) atoms remains hidden without neutron diffraction at the required pressures.

Much of the important science is outlined in Appendix C, here we highlight very recent claims of the *highest ever super-conducting temperature of 190K*, in H₂S at HP²⁸. If confirmed, a full structure determination of this material will be critical. Moreover, a clear isotope effect implies that H (or D) atoms play a key role in the mechanism of superconductivity (SC). At present, no instrument in the world is capable of revealing H(D) locations at sufficient pressure, but this would be within reach of ESPRESSO. Other key targets include pure silane in the 30 to 90 GPa range, the absence of neutron diffraction data so far having led to a lack of understanding of this complex system which exhibits insulator-metal transitions^{18,22,29,30}, HTSC¹⁹, P-induced amorphisation and polymerisation^{21,31}. Similar phenomena in germane and stannane (Appendix C) amplify the need for neutrons to locate H/D atoms bonded to increasingly heavy Group 14 atoms.

Metal hydrides also exhibit SC, including Pt-hydride, which is only stable above 70 GPa³²⁻³⁴. Neutron capabilities in this pressure range are critical to locate the D/H atoms adjacent to much heavier species and clarify their role in SC.

Light element alloys Synchrotrons are of limited use for measuring the lightest metals and their alloys (with special exceptions where single-crystals can be grown³⁵). Yet, significant scientific problems depend on precise measurements of stoichiometry and structure in these materials requiring neutrons. One example is found in the ammonia hydrates: ammonia and water form a unique "molecular alloy"³⁶ at HP. Key questions such as 'How does stoichiometry evolve?' and 'what is the nature of H-bonding?'

can only be addressed with neutrons. In a completely different system, theorists have begun to consider the Li/Be/B ternary system as a potential route to high T_c SC. In the Li:Be system, immiscible at ambient conditions, calculations³⁷ show a range of stoichiometries stabilise above 20 GPa. Further calculations show more structures stabilising at pressures up to 80 GPa³⁸. The proposed unit cells have a longest d-spacing of ~ 3.99 Å and low (monoclinic) symmetry demanding high $\delta d/d$ resolution $< 0.4\%$ to resolve peaks. As both Be and B¹¹ have extremely high coherent neutron cross-sections, neutrons are an ideal structural probe of stoichiometry and structure and only ESPRESSO can reach the relevant pressure range of 20-80 GPa.

Gas hydrates The discovery that gas hydrates persist to pressures in excess of 100 GPa³⁹ has opened up a whole new field. These dense phases have H-bond network geometries distinct from pure ice. For example, the "C₂" hydrogen hydrate⁴⁰ has a single H-bond network twice as compressible as the double network in ice VII suggesting elusive H-bond centring may occur at a modest 50 GPa. To study this, though, ESPRESSO must access reflections down to at least $d=0.5$ Å. Another important substance, methane hydrate, has many HP forms, some of which may account for methane in the atmosphere of Titan³⁹. ESPRESSO will characterise this and also behaviour in gas-water systems like N₂, CH₄(CD₄) and CO₂ hydrates. CO₂ hydrate is of particular interest because of the potential for network gas interactions and polymerisation of the gas.

1.1.2 Correlated electronic phenomena

The signature of strongly correlated materials is a multitude of competing ground states that can be manipulated by chemical composition, structure or strain state. These parameters adjust the fine interplay between structural, magnetic, electronic and orbital interactions that lie at the origin of phenomena including SC, piezoelectricity (PE) ferroelectricity (FE) or colossal magnetoresistance (CMR). These competing interactions display comparable energy scales making them difficult to decouple. Within this context, compression offers a powerful "tuning knob" for investigating how subtle changes in electron correlation lead to major changes in material behavior. In contrast with chemical doping, which introduces disorder and defects in the system, pressure is a "clean" way to manipulate properties, decoupling the interactions, controlling the bandwidth, and altering structure. This is a nascent field that ESPRESSO will be perfectly positioned to catalyse by offering the unique ability to measure nuclear and magnetic structure simultaneously at HP and, of equal importance, very low T.

Spin and magnetic transitions in 3d-transition metal compounds An important group of transition metal compounds are *Mott-Hubbard insulators*. The simplest examples are the 3D monoxides (e.g. NiO & FeO), minerals such as Fe₂O₃ and Fe₃O₄, and numerous ternary compounds such as rare earth (R) orthoferrites RFeO₃. HP allows tuning of the bandwidth as well as crystal field splitting, eventually leading to magnetic collapse, spin-pairing transition, metallization, and/or structural transition. Understanding the interplay and driving force between spin, orbital, magnetic, and lattice parameters in these systems at extreme conditions is of sharp, topical interest and ESPRESSO will revolutionise such studies. Its crystallographic scope will access the maximum d-spacings of 5Å that ambient pressure magnetic structures suggest are required. Meanwhile, subtle rhombohedral (or lower symmetry) distortions such as in Fe₃O₄⁴¹ will require its high crystallographic resolution.

HP studies have suggested complex behaviour involving intermediate high-spin to low-spin (HSLs) transitions such as in MnO⁴²⁻⁴⁴, PrFeO₃⁴⁵ and CaFe₂O₄⁴⁶, with some occurring at substantially different pressures than the insulator-metal transition. The case of Fe₂O₃ is particularly interesting since it appears only half of the Fe³⁺ in the HP phase transform to a LS state, whereas the rest retain high-spin configurations beyond 70 GPa⁴⁷. These HSLs transitions also have important geophysical implications as they affect important properties of

Figure 3 P-T diagram for SrFe₂As₂ illustrating interplay between magnetism, structure and superconductivity is probed with modest pressures².

Earth minerals including elasticity and conductivity⁴⁸. The only currently available probes for magnetism in this P range are synchrotron Mössbauer, photoemission spectroscopy and circular magnetic dichroism; *none of these probes can resolve magnetic and structural parameters directly.*

Superconductors P “activates” SC, almost doubling the number of elements that superconduct⁴⁹. And the record for highest T_c ever measured - 160K at 30 GPa in a cuprate⁵⁰ – may have recently been broken according to very recent claims of a 190K transition in H_2S ²⁸.

Neutron capability is powerful because antiferromagnetic (AFM) states are common to the phase diagrams of all HT SC's implying a relation between the two phenomena. ESPRESSO would be necessary to study this relation in the **cuprates** as their relatively low compressibility leads to interesting phenomena occurring only at multiple 10s of GPa (e.g the T_c maximum in $HgBa_2Ca_{m-1}Cu_mO_{2m+2+\delta}$ at 30 GPa⁵⁰) driving a clear need to study magnetic structure in this regime. Meanwhile, the **iron pnictide compounds** exhibit an especially intriguing interplay between magnetism and SC at much lower temperatures. ESPRESSO will access T approaching 1K with micro-sample volumes allowing vastly reduced pressure cell mass. The parent compounds of Fe-based SCs form layered structures with AFM order close to the SC transition^{51,52}. The onset of SC is believed to be related to the suppression of spin density waves (SDW) in the AFM state. This suppression can be achieved, in a highly controlled fashion, with P instead of conventional chemical doping² (Figure 3). Studying the structural and magnetic transitions in pnictides at HP LT is thus uniquely powerful in understanding the mechanism of unconventional SC's. Neutron diffraction is key for revealing this interplay, providing simultaneous access to nuclear and magnetic structures. However, up to now, *almost no studies of the P evolution of magnetic structure have been performed as a direct consequence of a lack of neutron capabilities at HP and LT.* In addition, these studies are crystallographically demanding: HP x-ray diffraction from $BaFe_2As_2$ (Section 1.2.6) benchmarks the required resolution at $<0.6\% \delta d/d$. Meanwhile, ambient-pressure neutron studies⁵² illustrate the need for intense cold flux: the longest magnetic Bragg peak is at 5.32 Å and has only ~1.5% the intensity of the strongest nuclear peak. At these long wavelengths, ESPRESSO will deliver 30 to 70-fold flux increases relative to competing instruments (see Section 1.2.4). Combined with the ability to trade this for resolution as required, ESPRESSO will be positioned to revolutionise such studies.

Perovskite materials Perovskite structures include materials used in a huge range of applications such as solid-oxide fuel cells, photovoltaics, solid-state lighting and lithium battery cathode material. They also exhibit a broad range of fundamental electronic phenomena including CMR, PE and FE and, of course, HTSC. CMR compounds are one example that illustrates the potential of neutron diffraction at high pressure. CMR is important for new electronic and spintronic devices and understanding its mechanism in term of basic electronic, structural and magnetic interactions is fundamental to their design. Since its discovery in hole-doped compounds, phase separation has been strongly linked to CMR and appears to be an intrinsic feature unrelated to grain boundary effects or to chemical doping, but which can be P-induced⁵³⁻⁵⁷. In pressure studies, gradual evolution from one phase to another is observed with the mixed phases extended over a wide P range. This behaviour may reflect competition between a metallic/ferromagnetic phase and an insulating/charge-ordered/antiferromagnetic phase, which are closely related to Jahn-Teller distortions that can be accurately quantified *in situ* by neutron diffraction. Neutron diffraction at high pressure also offers an opportunity to investigate the evolution of magnetic structures clarifying their relation to CMR.

As alluded to above, neutrons are indispensable probes of the subtle distortions of the O octahedra adjacent to heavy atoms. An unusual example is given by a study of $PbRuO_3$ up to 50 GPa which revealed the most distorted octahedra ever reported in a perovskite structure⁵⁸. In this study, two proposed structural models, differing only in their oxygen positions, *could not be resolved with x-ray data.* In addition to the problematic heavy cation x-ray signal, the relatively small magnitude of distortions is hidden by the form factor. ESPRESSO would be able to directly resolve these octahedral distortions that clearly have a critical role in properties. Yet, systematic studies of such systems (e.g. the $RMnO_3$ system with R=Pr,Nd,Tb,Dy,Ho,Er and Y) indicate typical octahedral strain is only ~0.02 to 0.1 Å demanding that ESPRESSO has an ability to measure reflections to at least $d=0.8$ Å. Meanwhile, as described previously, long wavelengths are equally critical, requiring optimal cold performance.

1.1.3 New Materials

Low dimensional and nanophase materials and glasses The last 2 decades have seen a huge increase in interest in nanophase materials, whose properties can differ wildly from the bulk. In such cases, neutron pair-distribution function (PDF) studies – giving the local distribution of atoms/nuclei – are extremely powerful. Neutrons can access high Q , while their isotope can selectively decouple contributions from distinct atomic species. As pressure acts on all lengthscales, the effect on properties obtained by tuning both local and nanostructure can be profound.

A key example is given by carbon and extreme P is indispensable for exploring its uniquely diverse bonding – in particular by tuning hybridisation. The rich tapestry of new **nanophase and low dimensional carbon materials** under pressure is barely explored. However, recent discoveries such as amorphous⁵⁹ and mesoporous diamond⁶⁰, and, most recently, 1D diamond nanothreads (Figure 4)⁶¹, hint at the enormous potential for forming useful materials. *Substantial kinetic effects limit the application of ab-initio theoretical techniques demanding in-situ data.* The case of nanothreads also illustrates the technical requirements: the primary diffraction feature is a large Bragg peak at 5.7Å requiring wavelengths of at least 8 Å, tensioned by the equally important need for high Q information with wavelengths as short as 0.65 Å for PDF studies.

Figure 4 Shows a TEM image of a cluster of nanothreads. Superimposed is an atomistic representation of the thread illustrating how it forms from benzene molecules irreversibly forced together by pressure.

There is also substantial interest in entirely non-crystalline materials, for example, **bulk metallic glasses**. In such systems, HP can form novel alloys by 'side-stepping' the Hume-Rothery rules (e.g. forming $\text{Ce}_3\text{Al}^{62}$). Meanwhile, P-induced crystallisation also revealed hidden long-range topological order in $\text{Ce}_3\text{Al}^{63}$. This example highlights the complementary nature of neutrons, which are sensitive to the Al atom locations all but hidden to x-ray techniques.

At a more fundamental level, there is deep interest in the ability of pressure to profoundly modify structure in glasses. For example, transitions between the amorphous ices⁶⁴ has been used as a proxy to study the 2nd critical point of liquid water. And, at much higher pressures, coordination changes in **tetrahedral glasses** such as SiO_2^{65} and GeO_2^{66-68} are still being intensely scrutinised. *ESPRESSO will be unique in the world in greatly expanding the pressure range for high-quality PDF measurements.* With all of the above systems, a minimum Q_{max} of 16 Å would make ESPRESSO comparable with typical high-pressure synchrotron beamlines.

New super-hard materials The hardest known materials are diamond and cubic boron nitride and the **CBN ternary** has long been considered the route to discovering new super-hard materials. The synthesis of such materials demands HPHT conditions that have, so far, precluded neutron characterisation. Yet neutrons are uniquely beneficial especially for understanding structure in noncrystalline- or nano-phases, which possess exceptional properties⁶⁹ e.g. aggregated diamond nanorods⁷⁰ are claimed to be the hardest material known. As C,B and N are very light elements, the requisite high Q information for such studies is not accessible, even at synchrotrons, due to the combination of weak x-ray scattering and the form factor. In contrast, all three elements are strong neutron scatterers and the marked diffraction contrast between N and the other ternary atoms confers an additional advantage of neutrons where N correlations are scientifically important.

1.1.4 Geoscience

Neutron diffraction is a powerful tool for the solution of problems in geoscience. It can distinguish between geologically important elements like iron and magnesium, and aluminium and silicon⁷¹. It is the best probe of how volatile species such as water and CO_2 interact with silicate minerals^{72,73}. It is indispensable for determining magnetic structures governing the magnetic field of the Earth and planets. And, finally, confers advantages in studies of liquids that make it ideal for determining structure in magmas⁷⁴. Current limits (25 GPa at room pressure and <10 GPa at 1500K) confine neutron studies to the PT conditions of only the upper part of the upper mantle. *ESPRESSO will revolutionise the field by accessing conditions spanning the entire mantle and reaching the core* (Figure 5).

Light elements in the core Although primarily formed from Ni and Fe, density estimates betray the presence of at least one light element in the Earth's core whose identity has been an enigma for over 60 years⁷⁵. Even small amounts of candidate materials (including Si, O, C, S and H – all but invisible to x-rays next to heavier Fe atoms) have dramatic effects on properties critical to modelling of the Core. By simultaneously reaching HP and HT, ESPRESSO will shed light on how these elements infiltrate the Fe lattice under conditions approaching the outer core of the Earth. This will provide our first clues as to how iron alloys with these materials.

Figure 5 Cross-section of the Earth showing seismic boundaries and corresponding PT regimes with current and future neutron capabilities.

silicon co-ordination change, at the 410-660km seismic anomaly (Figure 5), will explore water balance in this zone. At greater depths, neutron data will provide the first detailed information on water in mantle perovskite which accounts for a large proportion of the lower mantle and the post-perovskite (PPV) phase whose existence is responsible for the D'' anomaly at the bottom of the mantle (Figure 5). PPV is orthorhombic (Cmcm) and a highest d-spacing of 4.02 (at 121 GPa)⁸¹, parameters that must be accommodated by the crystallographic specification of ESPRESSO.

Anion and cation partitioning The mantle is composed of mixtures of oxide phases with disordered anions (Al/Si) and cations (principally Mg, Fe and Ca), and how these partition at depth is fundamental to models of the mantle. For example, it is not clearly understood how the compositions of the upper and lower mantle relate to each other. Uniquely, ESPRESSO will provide *in situ* microscopic data on these processes under the relevant PT. Similarly, studies at higher P will explore element partitioning in MgFeSiO₃ PPV – the most common mineral known. Finally ESPRESSO will extend neutron studies to revealing unique insight into iron partitioning between PPV and the core itself⁸².

Melt studies ESPRESSO will also provide crucial new information on geologic liquids (magmas): the incorporation of water in magmas has a profound effect on the deep-water cycle, but remains experimentally unexplored without neutron scattering. PDF data (requiring data to at least 16 Å⁻¹) from deuterated systems obtained on ESPRESSO would reveal the local deuteron correlations, helping identify how water is accommodated within the bulk melt.

1.1.5 Low and ambient pressure applications of ESPRESSO

Although the clear design brief for ESPRESSO is to enable very high-pressure diffraction, its instrumental characteristics will also add additional advantages not currently available at other high-pressure diffractometers. Due to a lack of space, these important applications of ESPRESSO are described in Appendix D.

Hydrous minerals An important on-going theme in Earth Science is the behaviour of water in the Deep Earth^{73,76}. Indeed the mantle may harbour more water than all of the oceans combined⁷⁷ and may be the source of the surface water that is critical for life. How water is cycled between mantle and oceans, where it resides in the mantle, and its effect on the mantle's properties are questions of huge importance that ESPRESSO will address at the microscopic level. Studies of candidate hydrous phases like hydrous aluminosilicate⁷⁸, newly discovered "Phase H" (MgSiO₂(OH)₂)⁷⁹ only stable above 48 GPa, and even nominally anhydrous phases (such as olivine, which is known to retain significant amounts of water) will explore their stability and the means by which they hold water across the entire range of conditions found in the mantle. Here, relatively low symmetries (hydrous aluminosilicate is trigonal, olivine orthorhombic) require a $\delta d/d$ of better than 0.6%⁸⁰. Neutron crystallographic refinements of these minerals as they pass through the 4-6 fold

1.2 DESCRIPTION OF INSTRUMENT CONCEPT AND PERFORMANCE

1.2.1 General concept

ESPRESSO will be a time-of-flight (ToF) diffractometer optimised for sample dimensions of order 1mm and below. This will make it ideal for *next-generation diamond-anvil cells* and the instrument will be optimised for these, achieving *unprecedented extremes of pressure*. Small samples will also revolutionise access to both *hot and cold extremes of temperature*, and these will be coupled with the new pressure capabilities. ESPRESSO will maximally exploit the intense, time-averaged pulses of the ESS to deliver the flux required for these micro samples. It will also use pulse-shaping choppers, and offer a tuneable pulse width that is linearly proportional to neutron wavelength allowing the flexibility to optimize for either flux or resolution depending on scientific need. To address the scientific demand for a wide Q-range, it will feature a spectral switch and view both thermal and cold segments of the baseline ESS butterfly moderator.

The detector array will be optimised for the finite angular aperture of pressure cells. Two detector banks will allow two complementary scattering geometries: a vertical 90° bank to maximise count rates and minimise background and a horizontal bank to maximise the range of scattering angles. The detectors will have a sufficiently high-level of pixilation to enable *both powder and single-crystal measurements*, and have minimal γ -ray sensitivity (cell collimation close sample environment will be an unavoidable source of secondary γ -radiation). Integral to the diffractometer design is direct access to the sample position, which will be close to waist height. An optical bench, cut around the detector banks, will enable a flexible modularity for different cell and collimation set-ups. This space will also be used for simultaneous online spectroscopy measurements and laser heating (exploiting the transparency of diamond-anvil pressure cells). This 'synchrotron-esque' appearance will reduce perceived barriers for new users entering the neutron community.

On ESPRESSO, sample environment is a mission-critical beamline component and is integral to this proposal. As discussed in Section 1.2.9, dedicated cells will be designed *in parallel with the instrument* to ensure optimal compatibility. The latest technical developments including ceramic and both single-crystal, and nano-polycrystalline diamond anvils will be exploited to minimise attenuation and backgrounds signals.

1.2.2 Comparable Instruments

There are three main instruments at neutron scattering facilities around the World that have been designed explicitly for optimised high-pressure diffraction measurements. The salient details of these dedicated instruments are summarised here:

Inst.Name	Facility, Country	Year ops	Max. P to date (GPa)	Primary flight path (optics)	Choppers	Mod.	Core sample-environment
PEARL ⁸³	ISIS, UK	1993	23	12.8m (No guide Line of sight)	None	100K CH ₄	P-E press
SNAP ⁸⁴	SNS, USA	2008	94	15.0m (Optional parabolic guide Line of sight)	T0 2xBandwidth	Poisoned, decoupled SC H ₂	P-E press, DAC
PLANET ⁸⁵	J-PARC, Japan	2013	20	25m (11.5m super-mirror guide)	T0 2xBandwidth	Decoupled H ₂	Multi-anvil, DAC

All of these instruments are ToF diffractometers and provide good comparisons for ESPRESSO. However, here we will focus on SNAP and PEARL, as PLANET has a somewhat different design, being optimised for a huge multi-axis press. In particular, SNAP is presently the only neutron diffractometer in the World to have measured diffraction intensities above 50 GPa (holding the current record of 94 GPa). Proposers Guthrie and Boehler led the SNAP diamond-anvil cell project that has clearly demonstrated both the feasibility and importance of an instrument optimised for microscopic samples¹⁶ (see Figure 6 and Appendix I).

Figure 6 Diffraction data from 3 separate $\sim 50\mu\text{g}$ samples of ice VII measured up to 43 GPa on SNAP¹⁶. The diffraction intensities are reproducible and quantitative and the data down to 0.6 Å were fully refineable. In the earliest data set, inadequate collimation led to weak contamination by the steel gasket containing the sample (marked *).

1.2.3 Wavelength range and Q coverage

Throughout the science case we have noted key instrumental parameters required to achieve the scientific goals. There is clearly a strong demand for intense flux in both the thermal and cold regimes and neither can be compromised. Cold neutrons with wavelengths as long as 5.5 to 8 Å are vital for crystallographic studies of methane; LiBeB alloys; magnetic systems; carbon nanomaterials and mineral systems. Meanwhile, studies of dense ice; hydrogen and deuterium; perovskites and PDF studies of liquids, glasses and nanophases materials necessitate wavelengths as low as 0.6 Å. Resolution demands are also variable: there are only moderate requirements for high symmetry (for example ice X) or single-crystal (pure H₂/D₂) systems, while a much higher specification is needed for lower symmetry powder crystallography (e.g. the gas hydrates, Li-Be-B alloys, Fe-pnictide superconductors and perovskites) where $\delta d/d$ as low as 0.4% is required.

The ESPRESSO wavelength requirements are incorporated into Table 2, which illustrates how these combine with angular coverage to give d and Q limits, and compared with SNAP and PEARL.

INSTRUMENT and SETUP	λ_{\min}	λ_{\max}	$2\theta_{\min}$	$2\theta_{\max}$	d_{\min}	d_{\max}	Q_{\min}	Q_{\max}
ESPRESSO 90° bank	0.60	8.00	60.0	120.0	0.346	8.000	0.785	18.138
ESPRESSO 90° bank (restricted)	0.60	8.00	80.0	100.0	0.392	6.223	1.010	16.044
ESPRESSO horiz. bank	0.60	8.00	30.0	150.0	0.311	15.455	0.407	20.232
SNAP 90° (1 st frame)	0.50	3.65	67.5	112.5	0.301	3.285	1.913	20.897
SNAP 90° (restricted)	0.50	3.65	80.0	100.0	0.354	2.839	2.213	19.253
SNAP high angle	0.50	3.65	112.5	157.5	0.255	2.195	2.863	24.650
SNAP low angle	0.50	3.65	26.0	71.0	0.431	8.113	0.774	14.595
SNAP 90° (2 nd frame)	3.70	6.50	67.5	112.5	2.225	5.850	1.074	2.824
SNAP 90° (restricted)	3.70	6.50	80.0	100.0	2.616	5.056	1.243	2.602
SNAP high angle	3.70	6.50	112.5	157.5	1.886	3.909	1.607	3.331
SNAP low angle	3.70	6.50	26.0	71.0	3.186	14.448	0.435	1.972
PEARL 90° bank	0.50	5.50	81.2	98.8	0.329	4.226	1.487	19.083
PEARL low-angle bank	0.50	5.50	20.0	60.0	0.500	15.837	0.397	12.566
PEARL high-angle bank	0.50	5.50	100.0	160.0	0.254	3.590	1.750	24.751

Table 2 Reciprocal space coverage for ESPRESSO and comparable instruments. As most of the instruments are able to explore several geometries, the extremes of these are considered. Also, as the pressure cell constrains diffraction angle (increasingly with pressure), a "restricted" geometry of $\pm 10^\circ$ in 2θ is considered (from the existing SNAP DAC designs). The blue figures indicate the most comparable geometries for each instrument.

A glance at Table 2 shows that ESPRESSO needs a notably wider wavelength range than the other HP instruments (particularly towards the cold end of the spectrum). In order to achieve this, ESPRESSO will have the option to view either the cold or thermal ESS sources by means of a translatable mirror assembly. As described in Section 1.2.4 this will deliver dramatic flux gains at longer wavelengths without compromise to thermal flux. For these low-energy neutrons, attenuation of pressure cell materials was considered and shown to be tractable at least to 8.0 Å (see Appendix F).

In the thermal regime, the shortest wavelength of 0.6Å covers the envisaged science programme and is competitive with the other HP instruments. As discussed in Section 1.2.5 the envisaged guide provides acceptable brilliance transfer even for these short wavelengths. Although 0.6 Å leads to a Q_{\max} that is slightly lower than both SNAP and PEARL, we expect to gain from reduced backgrounds resulting

from ESPRESSO's long curved guide. Experience on SNAP and PEARL is that background introduces a lower practical limit on Q_{\max} ($\sim 16\text{-}18\text{\AA}$ for most systems) lower than that shown in Table 2.

1.2.4 Moderator choice and flux comparison with competing instruments

The only way to achieve the required broad wavelength band is to access both the cold and thermal sources of the ESS. In order to do this without compromise, we propose a design with a 'spectral switch': a movable mirror that images the cold source when needed, but can be translated out of the beam to provide un-occluded access to the thermal source. This concept is similar to a design

Figure 7 (Upper panel) Calculated flux curves comparing ESPRESSO with existing and future high-pressure diffractometers at similar $\delta d/d$ resolutions. Frames 2,3&4 correspond to the cold source (Lower panel). Flux at 1.4\AA as a function of resolution.

wavelengths available on SNAP of $\sim 6.5\text{\AA}$, where it exceeds a factor of 70. Across the wavelength range of 1 to 6.5\AA , the average gain factor over SNAP is 33.

proposed in the MAGIC proposal to increase cold flux. The disadvantage of having to mechanical switch between modes is not perceived as severe and a time step comparable to that of re-phasing the choppers would be introduced as a design constraint. Kinematic translations will negate any need to re-calibrate after switching.

For the mirror itself, we propose to use a design similar to other instruments at the ESS, for example, DREAM, which has been well characterised. Following this work, we propose a solid-state Si-bender at $\sim 6\text{m}$, which will be accessible should any repair or adjustment be required. The current DREAM design employs a multi-channel bender with a coating of $m=2.87$, and a length of 60.5mm . The corresponding parameters for the ESPRESSO mirror will be optimised during the detailed design phase of the instrument.

Figure 7 shows the calculated flux at the sample position for ESPRESSO compared to PEARL, u-PEARL (after a proposed TS1 target upgrade) and SNAP all at comparable $\delta d/d$ resolutions (see Technical Appendix G for calculation details)^a. In this calculation, we have used the calculated brightness of the 3cm "butterfly" moderator in the current baseline. Figure 7 shows ESPRESSO will substantially out-perform its strongest competitor SNAP above 0.75\AA in this like-for-like comparison^b. At lower wavelengths, we expect to remain competitive through background mitigation inherent in our long flight path. Above 0.75\AA , the gain factor relative to SNAP rises rapidly, peaking at 10 and staying above 8 for the remainder of the thermal region.

Meanwhile, above $\sim 2\text{\AA}$, the cold source clearly comes into its own, increasing gain to a factor of 20 by 2.5\AA . At still higher wavelengths, the gain continues to increase up to the longest

^a The calculation includes guide transport but not collimation. For the proposed double-aperture set up, this is simply a multiplication by the filling factor described in Section 1.2.5. Although this reduces flux by up to 30% for the smallest samples, similar factors also affect SNAP and PEARL so the comparison remains valid.

^b The ESPRESSO bandwidth is less than SNAP (1.8\AA vs 4.3\AA). When it's necessary to collect data across a more than a single frame, this effectively reduces gain by an additional factor of n , the number of frames.

In addition, and in contrast with short-pulse instruments, ESPRESSO will have the option of substantially increasing this flux further by sacrificing resolution (lower panel Figure 7). This would allow

Figure 8 Panel A shows a plan view of the two diamonds and metal gasket that form the pressurized chamber of a diamond cell. In this geometry, the beam touches nothing but single-crystal diamond and sample. Panel B shows a close up of the sample, the 500µm diameter corresponds to a sample that can be driven to over 40 GPa. Panel C shows the umbra and penumbra relating to Panel B, defining the diameter of the umbra as $2r_u$ and the extent of the penumbra as p .

a further factor of 2-3 increase (see Section 1.2.7). In studies of high symmetry systems, or single-crystal samples, where large peak widths do not hamper the extraction of precise intensities, this would allow total gains over SNAP of well over 2 orders of magnitude, particularly at longer wavelengths.

1.2.5 Choice of beam size and guide design

Beam Size The choice of a small beam is a defining characteristic of the ESPRESSO instrument and optimisation for samples diameters of $\leq 1\text{mm}$ will revolutionise extreme-conditions neutron research. The beam must also be tightly controlled in order to enter and exit the sample environment with minimal

Table 3 Typical sample size and forces required for a given pressure in existing neutron DACs¹

Max.P (GPa)	Diameter anvil tip (mm)	Force (metric tonnes)	Sample diameter (µm)
2	2.5 ^a	1.5	1000 ^a
5	2.5 ^a	4	1000
10	2.0	5	800
25	2.0	11	800
50	1.4	11	550
100	1.0	11	400

interaction. This places stringent demands on ESPRESSO's beam and – consequently – its guide design.

It also requires sophisticated alignment and collimation procedures. Figure 8 illustrates this challenge by showing a diamond cell in transmission geometry as envisaged when using ESPRESSO's 90° detector banks. The dimensions are comparable with those that have exceeded 40 GPa on SNAP (see Table 3 and data in

Figure 6). An optimal beam must pass cleanly through the gasket hole, while illuminating as large a volume of the sample as possible. This corresponds to maximising the umbra and minimising the penumbra of the beam, giving a total beam diameter \leq the sample diameter. This also introduces a need for alignment that is accurate to the level of $<10\mu\text{m}^a$ (discussed further in Section 1.2.9).

Guide design ESPRESSO will be a very long instrument - about 170 m from source to sample. This length is critical to enable maximal use of the long pulse of the ESS while maintaining high diffraction resolution. A guide of this length will allow a wavelength band of 1.8 Å and enable a flexible trade-off between resolution and flux by varying the opening time and separation of two pulse-shaping choppers, placed close to the target monolith wall (Section 1.2.7).

^a We note that such precision is trivial on modern synchrotrons. This uses a scanning methodology that has also been demonstrated to be effective for neutrons on SNAP.

Figure 9 Upper Panel shows optimum radius of downstream aperture as a function of position for a range of sample diameters. Lower Panel shows the corresponding filling fractions

collimator piece formed from hexagonal BN. Using this design, the final aperture could be positioned within 5mm of the sample (almost touching the upstream diamond, which was ~3.5mm thick).

The detailed geometry of a double aperture system is described in Appendix J. Using the equations given there, we have considered the case for a range of typical sample sizes. In these calculations, the total divergence was taken to be 0.5° (8.73 mrad), and the first aperture fixed at a distance of 2m upstream of the sample, just in front of the end of the ESPRESSO guide. Then, for various locations of the downstream pinhole, x_2 , the maximum “filling fraction”, f (the fraction of the maximum possible beam that illuminates the sample, see Appendix J) was calculated. This was repeated for various sample diameters ensuring in each case that the total beam diameter did not exceed these. The results in Figure 9 show that aperture 2 must be held close to the sample, particularly for the smallest samples.

Although the position of aperture 2 introduces some engineering constraints, the double pin-hole set up has proven quite tractable as shown by the work on SNAP. The SNAP pressure cells (see Section 1.2.9) and collimation were specially designed to position the final aperture within 5mm of the sample. This was achieved with an extended hBN collimator tube that reached inside the pressure cell so that its tip (housing the final aperture) almost touched the back of the upstream diamond anvil). A similar design would enable a filling fraction of 73% for even the smallest sample considered here (which would easily exceed 100 GPa). Increasing the sample to more standard sizes takes f into the 82-90% range.

In order to achieve the required small, well-controlled beams of arbitrary diameter, we considered three cases:

- Beam shaping using pinhole apertures with a straight conventional guide
- Beam shaping using pinhole apertures with a curved conventional guide
- A Selene-type focusing guide⁸⁶.

While pinhole apertures offer the simplest solution, they require that the final collimation be placed close to the sample position. The Selene guide avoids this and is able to transport an image of the source some distance from the end of the guide. All three cases were compared using the Guide_bot optimizer⁸⁷ as shown in Appendix E. Despite its advantages, the Selene guide delivers a vastly lower divergence than the conventional guides, particularly at essential short wavelengths. For an instrument where maximal flux is critical, it is clear that traditional guides provide the best engineering solution for ESPRESSO.

Double pinhole apertures These represent the simplest solution for adapting divergence and beam size to match a given sample. They can be readily implemented through the insertion of variable apertures between the end of the guide and the sample. The divergence is then defined by the position and size of the first (upstream) aperture, with the total beam size controlled by the second aperture (closest to the sample). Here, we have considered the case illustrated in Figure 8. We note that a similar geometry was successfully employed on SNAP, using a fine, tubular

This fine control would even be accessible for samples contained in a cryostat. Here, it would be necessary to mount the final aperture to the cell body. This has also been tested and demonstrated feasible on SNAP, however with reduced flexibility to fine-tune the position of the collimator. On ESPRESSO, a more advanced design is envisaged using cryogenic-capable translation stages. Such stages, based on piezo drives and capable of operation down to 2K, are commercially available^a. In order to address this issue and to ensure an optimum and easy-to-use collimation setup, we will prioritise an engineering study for mounting and aligning the downstream pinhole during the preliminary engineering phase of the instrument. This will include appropriate prototypes and online testing as described in Section 1.2.9.

Figure 10 (Left) Geometry of straight guide, i.e. one allowing direct line-of-sight (LOS) between moderator and sample. (Right) Geometry of curved guide, i.e. avoiding direct LOS.

Straight versus curved guide comparison In this proposal, we first considered the relative merits of a curved versus a straight guide. The lower background expected from the former is tempered by the possibility of reduced brilliance transfer for the shortest wavelengths. In order to assess the performance of both guide-types, optimal geometries for a thermal source were determined using the Guide_bot optimiser⁸⁷. Figure 10 shows the results for each guide, while Figure 11 shows the corresponding brilliance transfers.

It is seen that the straight guide provides more than 50% brilliance transfer (BT) for all wavelengths above about 0.75 Å within a divergence interval of ±0.7°, with a brilliance transfer above 70% for wavelengths in the 1-5 Å range. Surprisingly, the curved guide was found to give comparable

Figure 11 (Left) Brilliance transfer as a function of wavelength and divergence for the guide geometry allowing direct LOS. (Right) Brilliance transfer as a function of wavelength and divergence for the guide geometry avoiding direct LOS. Black curve shows the optimised performance, red curve shows a guide impaired by either misalignment or radiation damage. The divergence plots below correspond to the wavelengths shown as coloured crosses in the wavelength-dependence plots.

^a e.g. Janssen Precision Engineering's CTS stages <http://www.jpe.nl/products/cryo-translation-stage/>

Figure 12 (2 Left hand frames) Beam profile for the straight guide. (2 right-hand frames) Beam profile for the curved guide. The beam profiles are shown for wavelengths of 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25 and 1.5 Å with colours corresponding to + symbols in Figure 11.

performance at short wavelengths even down to 0.5Å, meanwhile at wavelengths above about 4 Å it performs less well. We believe this is due to a gravity effect that can be avoided by simply combining the vertical geometry of the straight guide with the horizontal geometry of the curved guide.

For all calculations, the guide is constrained to end 2 m before the sample. This allows space for inserting the double-pinhole optics, eliminating unwanted neutrons at a sufficient distance before the sample to minimize the background on the instrument. The pin-hole optics will then select the desired divergence and beam size at the sample, up to the guide limit of ±0.7°. In this way, the flux at the sample can be traded for resolution as required by experimental needs.

Finally, Figure 12 shows the beam spot at the sample, obtained with pinholes suitable for a 500µm sample diameter (that is $x_1=2m$, $r_1=17.603mm$ and $x_2=6mm$, $r_2=202\mu m$). This provides a divergence at the sample of ±0.5° with the penumbra staying entirely within the 500 µm sample to avoid gasket scatter.

Selene calculation In addition to the conventional guides, guide_bot was also used to explore the Selene geometry. Figure 13 shows the result of this optimization and compares this with the conventional guides. As seen in the figure, the selene guide was seen to transport around a factor of 10 less flux at all wavelengths.

Summary of guide design choice

On the basis of the calculations described above, our preference is for the curved guide transporting a maximal divergence of ±0.7°, ending

Figure 13 The intensity between fixed divergence limits is compared for both line-of-sight and curved conventional guides and for a Selene-type guide. These calculations represent the case for a nominal 500 µm sample. The effect of gravity is evident for the curved guide above ~ 4Å. As described in the text, this can be accounted for.

at 2 m before the sample. This will be followed by a series of interchangeable pin-holes that allow the beam divergence and beam size to be tailored to specific sample size and resolution requirements.

The second pin-hole, which defines the beam size, needs to be placed very close to the sample and priority will be given to ensure that good engineering solutions will be found. Experience from SNAP indicates that this is entirely feasible and this is discussed further in Section 1.2.9.

Although the Selene system negates the need for such pin-holes by transporting only the useful divergence and beam-size through the guide system, there is a substantial cost in terms of flux. Moreover, it cannot provide a sufficiently large divergence at short wavelengths to flexibly tailor the resolution, as will be outlined in more detail in the next sections. Final deciding factors are that the conventional guides represent a more mature and well-understood technology and are associated with both lower levels of risk and cost.

Having chosen the optimized guide design for a thermal source, further guide_bot simulations were conducted to also optimise for cold neutrons. This work is ongoing and would continue well into detailed design stage. However, initial calculations indicate that substantial improvements in brilliance

transfer (Figure 14) at long wavelengths are possible with only negligible impact on the short wavelength performance.

Figure 14 Preliminary design for both thermal and cold optimised guide shows the potential to correct the reduced longer wavelength performance of the curved guide seen in Figure 11

1.2.6 Resolution demands on instrument

In addition to optimising for flux, any powder diffractometer must also deliver sufficient resolution. As detailed in the science case, there are several instances where resolution must be better than 0.5% $\delta d/d$. Uniquely on ESPRESSO, the flexible nature of the long-pulse source allows *optimisation for either resolution or flux*. This conveys an enormous advantage, as the importance of these two competing parameters vary wildly from experiment-to-experiment.

One example where resolution, not flux, is crucial is the case of the Fe-based superconductors (Section 1.1.2). Here, modest pressures allow relatively large samples, but a key experimental challenge is to resolve tetragonal-to-orthorhombic splitting (concurrently with the appearance of magnetic peaks). We simulated diffraction patterns for $BaFe_2As_2$ using the parameters in Table 4 (taken from Huang *et al*⁵²) considering the 90° detector bank and assuming 0.5° total divergence.

T (K)	S.G.	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)
175	<i>I 4/mmm</i>	3.95702	3.95702	12.9685
5	<i>Fmmm</i>	5.61587	5.57125	12.9428

Table 4 Lattice parameters for $BaFe_2As_2$

The upper plot using 147 μ s of the ESS pulse corresponds to the flux calculation in Figure 7 and shows that the splitting of the 220 is just resolvable, even at low angle. However, by reducing the time slice (and flux) by only $\sim 30\%$,

Figure 15 Calculated diffraction patterns for $BaFe_2As_2$ for constant divergence of 0.5° showing the 220 reflection. The left column shows data measured at the lowest angle and the right column the highest angle of the ESPRESSO 90° detector bank. Top row shows a pulse width of 147 μ s (corresponding to flux calculation) in Figure 7. In the lower row, this has been reduced to 100 μ s.

ESPRESSO is able to enhance resolution as required. The effect of tunable resolution is shown in Figure 15, while Figure 7 illustrates its full scope and the effect on flux.

1.2.7 Chopper assembly

In order to make full use of the flexibility offered by a long-pulse source, ESPRESSO requires a means by which the pulse width can be tuned to select the required resolution. In addition, a pulse width that scales proportionally with T is also desirable, to ensure constant resolution across the full wavelength band. These requirements can be satisfied by a pair of disk-choppers operating in, so-called, "double-blind" mode (see description in Appendix G).

The flux calculations shown in Figure 7 used an opening time of $147\mu\text{s}$ (at 1\AA), corresponding to a chopper separation of 58cm. Although this gives a comparable resolution to PEARL or SNAP, the resulting wavelength-dependent pulse width is roughly 10 times greater (reflecting the ~ 10 times longer flight path). Despite this, even by 6\AA (where the width is 0.882 ms), less than 30% of the total 2.86ms pulse width is used. Correspondingly, *by degrading diffraction resolution*, a further factor of over 3 in flux is realisable.

In order to allow the possibility to realise this tradeoff, the separation between two pulse-shaping choppers (PSC1 and PSC2, see Figure 16) should be variable between about 20 and 150 cm. This can be achieved by placing PSC2 on movable mountings. Although this allows the desired complete flexibility to choose between flux and resolution this arrangement would clearly preclude a guide section between the two choppers. This will be thoroughly investigated during the preliminary engineering design stage. Should this cause unacceptable loss in guide performance, an alternative design, with 2-3 additional choppers *at fixed distances* would allow for discrete modes of operation. In addition to the PSC's, two choppers will also be required placed at 10 and 25m. These would allow the arbitrary shifting of the finite wavelength band ($\sim 1.8\text{\AA}$) to the desired range for each experiment, while preventing frame overlap.

Figure 16 Sketch of proposed chopper assembly showing the spectral switch, two pulse-shaping choppers (PS1 and PS2, the latter being movable), and the two bandwidth-choppers (BW1 and BW2).

1.2.8 Detector Geometry and Technology

Geometry The scattering geometry of ESPRESSO will be optimised for opposed anvil pressure devices. As shown in Figure 17, these designs will have a fixed angular aperture of size α relative to the equator of the cell. As a general rule, α will be *minimised* in cells designed for the *highest* pressures requiring the largest forces and, therefore, the most massive anvil support. Within ESPRESSO's suite of pressure cells α is expected to range from 10 to 30° .

ESPRESSO's main detector bank will lie on a plane perpendicular to the incident beam. The symmetry of this arrangement will allow the counts from all detectors to be summed, maximising statistics. In this geometry, the beam will enter and exit through the anvils (vertically in Figure 17). It will subtend angles of $60 < 2\theta < 120^\circ$ to accommodate the largest scattering aperture α envisaged^a. The detectors will lie on an arc with a radius of 600mm. A gap at the top of this arc will allow overhead access for craning of larger equipment, such as cryostats.

Figure 17 Illustration of an opposed anvil design with a conical support arrangement as used on SNAP¹. Irrespective of incident beam direction, the aperture of the diffracted beam is limited by the angle α .

^a This total angle of 60° has been realized in cells such as the "panoramic cell" for over 2 decades. Initially developed for inelastic x-ray scattering measurements, this design has now been used with many techniques including neutron diffraction.

Figure 18 (A) Diffractometer operating in 90° and (B) horizontal modes, in both, green indicates both incident and diffracted neutron paths. (C) The open nature of the instrument allows direct access to the pressure cell and surround. (D) An online optical spectrometer will take Raman data and measure pressure. The extended optical bench will enable a modular set-up akin to a synchrotron beamline.

In order to extend angular coverage, substantially increasing Q range (in particular for cases where α is less than 30° e.g. for very-high pressure cells), a second detector bank is envisaged. In order to use this, an alternative scattering geometry, with the pressure cell axis vertical and the beam entering through the gasket, would be employed. In this case, the required $\pm 30^\circ$ coverage would extend above and below the equatorial plane of the instrument. In this mode, angular coverage would be substantially extended from 30° to 150° in 2θ . In practice, a portion of the detector bank will always be occluded by cell supports, and a separate data collection (with the cell rotated about a vertical axis) would be necessary to access these.

Detector technology There are several key requirements for the ESPRESSO detector arrays:

- Good γ -ray discrimination.
- Good short wavelength efficiency.
- Sufficient pixel densities to resolve single-crystal reflections requiring, maximally, a $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ pixel size (Appendix H).

An important factor in selecting detector technology is the total count rate per pixel. Likely the most intense neutron flux seen by the ESPRESSO detectors will come from single-crystal diamond spots, which are not expected to exceed $\sim 500 \text{ kHz/ch}$ (see Appendix H). These relatively low count rates are a natural consequence of the small beam size, and give ESPRESSO a wide choice of different technologies. He^3 detectors were precluded from consideration as a consequence of cost and increasing supply challenges, so in this proposal, we considered:

- Scintillators (ZnS/LiF) with wavelength shifting fibres with either multianode photomultiplier tubes or, alternatively, silicon photomultipliers
- ¹⁰B-based detectors with layers angled with respect to the beam axis.

Both detection technologies are evolving rapidly and it is difficult at this stage to decide unambiguously on which would be most appropriate for ESPRESSO. A final decision would be a priority of the preliminary engineering phase of the instrument, likely involving online tests with pressure cells. However, the flexibility, demonstrated capability to achieve the required 2 dimensional pixel densities, and relative maturity of scintillator technology do appear to make this the preferable choice at this early stage.

1.2.9 Sample stages, collimation and scanning

As described previously, micro-samples require sophisticated alignment procedures. On ESPRESSO, these will be based on scanning methodologies that, although fairly novel with neutrons, are very mature on synchrotron sources. Preliminary work on the SNAP beamline has demonstrated the simplicity with which these techniques are adapted to neutron use.

The basic principle is to scan an object through the beam, measuring transmitted intensity versus motor drive position. ESPRESSO has a downstream monitor for this purpose. A two-step procedure will be employed whereby firstly, the final collimator is aligned to the neutron beam and, secondly, the sample is aligned to the beam passing through the final collimator.

In order to place the final aperture as close as possible to the sample, the collimator will have a tubular design similar to that shown in Figure 19. The long aspect ratio requires that, both yaw and pitch of the collimator must also be scanned to ensure perfect parallelism, prior to additional scans to centre on the beam.

Figure 19 Sketch of final collimator piece. In order to align the collimator, 4 motions are required: translations along z and x (into page) directions and rotations about these same axes. The final tip is exchangeable depending on the required beamsize. The tip shown has an inner diameter of 500µm. A sliding, kinematic mount allows the collimator to be retracted for insertion of the pressure cell.

Once the collimator is aligned, the pressure cell is then mounted in the instrument. An optical system will suffice to position the cell within 20-30µm of the instrument centre. Subsequently, the sample will be scanned relative to the micro-beam passing through the collimator to fine tune the position to within 2µm.

In addition to the motors required to achieve scanning, the sample mount will also sit on an omega table, allowing rotation about a vertical axis. This will serve several purposes including angular studies of microstructure, angular exploration of reciprocal space for single-crystal samples and the ability to extend Q range for pressure cells with limited scattering apertures.

1.2.10 Sample environment, online laser systems and ancillary DAC laboratory.

As has been mentioned previously, sample environment (SE) forms a key component of this proposal. By designing both instrument and SE concurrently, it is possible to optimally match parameters. For example, detectors angles are mapped to cell apertures, pressure cells modified to accommodate incident beam collimation and diffracted beam collimation prepared with idealised gauge volumes. In addition, sample workflow during experiments can also be streamlined through careful consideration of the interfaces between instrument and sample environment. The sample environment component of the ESPRESSO proposal is designed to harmonise with the wider provision for high-pressure capabilities within ESS Science Support Systems for avoiding any duplication and leveraging capabilities that are independent of this proposal (for example: gas-loading capability and general equipment such as compressors, vacuum pumps and presses).

Of the ESPRESSO-specific technologies that are part of the present proposal, 4 main projects exist:

- A research and development program targeting new diamond-anvil cell designs optimised for the ESPRESSO geometry, collimation and other, coupled, environments enabling temperature control.
- An online (laser-based) optical system enabling in situ pressure measurement and Raman spectroscopy.
- An ancillary loading laboratory for preparing, characterising and loading DACs.
- A laser-heating system delivering temperatures of ~2000K concurrently with sample pressurisation.

The first of these projects - the targeted development of new pressure cells - is vital because the intense flux of ESPRESSO can only be fully exploited by mating the pressure hardware to the neutron instrumentation. We will take as a starting point the latest designs developed on SNAP and optimise these for ESPRESSO. By developing multiple models in parallel, each targeting a difference pressure range, we will be able to maximise the scientific scope of the instrument. Details of the R&D programme are given in Appendix K

In addition to cell designs we will further exploit the optical transparency of diamond to enable *in situ* spectroscopic measurements. In a high-pressure experiment, *where structure is a variable, such ancillary probes are indispensable*. Another key advantage will be the enabling of optical pressure measurement – via ruby fluorescence – negating the need to include calibrants within sample loadings (minimising background and spurious diffraction peaks). Systems of this ilk are standard on many synchrotron beamlines and the open design of the diffractometer will easily accommodate the optical components.

In order to support the operations on the instrument, it will be critical to have an ancillary laboratory proximate to the diffractometer. This must provide a clean and quiet space for preparing and characterising DAC loadings. It is anticipated that pressure cells used on ESPRESSO may have measurable levels of activation leading to the requirement of a dedicated handling facility. Basic loading equipment including microscopes, a ruby fluorescence spectrometer and gasket drilling equipment will be included.

A large number of the science challenges (particularly in the geosciences, see Section 1.1.4) that ESPRESSO will address for the first time require temperatures well in excess of current capabilities. We propose to exploit the optical transparency of diamond to develop online laser heating. This technology is standard on several HP synchrotron beamlines and we will adapt it for our larger volume neutron cells.

1.2.11 Software

The analysis of data from ESPRESSO will require powerful, yet nimble software tools. A key challenge is to select active areas of the detectors not occluded by the pressure cell and to mask out contaminant scattering (for example single-crystal diamond spots). In addition, accurate intensities require real-time attenuation corrections that adapt to the changing geometry and attenuation characteristics of the cells as they are pressurised. Indeed, the attenuation correction has been the subject of substantial research on SNAP and has been shown to be amenable to a semi-empirical approach (see Appendix L). This is part of a wealth of software already developed in the MANTID framework will be optimised for ESPRESSO with the aim of making data reduction rapid and easy for experimental users.

In addition to data processing, the control of the variety of motors necessary to align the cell will be developed along with easy-to-use and robust graphical user interfaces (again, we expect to build on synchrotron expertise here). In addition to working closely with the ESS motor control group, we will also vigorously pursue collaboration with MAX-VI the DMSC to optimally deliver the required software.

1.3 TECHNICAL MATURITY

The ESPRESSO risk profile benefits from intrinsically simple, robust and proven instrumentation. Although there are elements of the proposal that require some R&D, these are primarily associated with sample environment, which is a relatively minor (~ 6%) component of the costing.

Guide: Although a long guide is needed, this will be constructed using “conventional” technologies that are mature and well understood. Long guides are intrinsic to any ESS instrument using requiring high TOF resolution and many instruments have settled on the 170m standard. With the concentrated design effort and resources of all of these instruments, any risk associated with the guide should be mitigated

Chopper assembly: ESPRESSO will use a relatively simple chopper array comprising two pulse-shaping choppers (PSCs) and two bandwidth choppers. A T0 chopper will not be necessary as the guide will be curved. At this stage, no extraordinary requirements are needed of the choppers themselves, which will conform to ESS standards. Some element of risk is attributable to the requirement that the location of the downstream PSC be variable. However, this instrumentation is not unique and will be implemented for other ESS instruments, including ODIN, which is already in the construction phase. One uncertainty at present is whether the extra space requirement for a moveable chopper will introduce substantial modification to the guide design. This question will be addressed during the engineering design stage and any resultant guide modifications are unlikely to introduce additional cost as this is determined primarily by length.

Diffraction: The key elements of the diffractometer are all considered low risk. The two geometries chosen: a main 90° bank and a supplementary horizontal bank are dictated by the nature of opposed-anvil pressure vessels. The design is similar to the mature PEARL diffractometer at ISIS (although both of its detector banks are vertical) and this has proven to be well suited to the task of measuring diffraction data from (large) opposed anvil Paris-Edinburgh cells. At present, we are inclined to pursue established detector technology – ZnS/Li⁶ scintillator glass. Using this mature technology will essentially mitigate almost all risk. If better technical options were found to be feasible (and to convey significant advantages e.g. in γ sensitivity and efficiency curves) during the engineering design phase these would be considered, but do not appear to be critical to delivering the scientific goals. As many other instruments will also be considering different detector technologies, information on these will rapidly amass and hopefully will minimise risk.

The decision to build the instrument without a vacuum tank is also not unique. PEARL, SNAP and PLANET all have this open design and, in addition to the streamlining operation, this will also simplify the design and manufacture of the diffractometer while reducing cost.

New pressure cells: Although a period of R&D is required to design optimal pressure cells, this will be built on a strong technological foundation and will benefit from many decades of combined experience in cell design (much of which will be contributed through in kind support, see Section 1.4). As repeated throughout the proposal, the development work on SNAP has led to working prototype cells. Although not optimal, these are already capable of covering much of the pressure demands made on ESPRESSO and, thus, the risk that the required pressures are unachievable is completely negated.

Laser optics, alignment motors and controls: The proposed spectroscopic instrumentation is identical to that found in laboratories and online at synchrotron beamlines. The only potential risk perceived is the possibility of radiation damage to the detector electronics. This risk can be mitigated by ensuring adequate shielding of sensitive components. Although much of the proposed alignment procedures and associated motion control are not standard at neutron sources, they are ubiquitous at synchrotrons. Several of the proposers and technical advisors to ESPRESSO are synchrotron experts and well qualified to ensure a working and user-friendly set up. In addition, the ESS benefits from the proximity of the MAX-IV synchrotron, which represents a substantial resource to address any unforeseen issues. Experience on SNAP has shown that the basics of synchrotron scan-based alignment are readily transferrable to neutron sources. Finally, co-proposers Guthrie and Bull are currently involved in a funded project to implement similar capabilities on the PEARL diffractometer at ISIS. This will provide a real-world testing ground for the equipment and software.

1.4 IN KIND CONTRIBUTIONS TO PROJECT

Partners are already established for sample environment component of this proposal, these principally include: Stefan Klotz (UPMC, France), Konstantin Kamenev and Eugene Gregoryanz (CSEC, UK) and Craig Bull (STFC, UK). Various IK projects led by these partners have been considered.

The pressure cell R&D project will rely heavily on the 2 decades of expertise in neutron pressure cell design and development in Paris (Klotz) and Edinburgh (Kamenev). Design parameters will be optimised through a combination of offline testing and finite element analysis (Kamenev). Online testing will be conducted at ISIS, on the PEARL diffractometer (Bull). These, ESPRESSO-specific IK projects could form part of more global activity within the Pressure Platform of ESS Science Support Systems and there will be substantial opportunities for synergies.

In addition to pressure cell development, expertise within CSEC (Gregoryanz) enables the proposed spectrometer and laser heating system to be considered as a feasible in kind work package.

1.5 COSTING

The ESPRESSO instrument has a relatively simple guide and diffractometer design, helping to keep costs under control. The main (and unavoidable) cost element is the guide system, this is followed by the detectors, although as the detector coverage, by design, is limited to match the finite apertures of the pressure cells this cost is relatively modest.

Integrated design: Full time effort for a Lead Scientist and Engineer and other scientists and engineers involved in instrument design and commissioning.

Systems integration: Systems engineering to ensure compatibility between components and compliance with ESS standards.

Detector and data acquisition: The ESPRESSO diffractometer comprises two banks of detectors that share one module at their intersection. The required detector coverage in the 90° bank is ~ 1.9m² with an additional 0.6m² for the horizontal bank giving a total requirement of 2.5m². Consultation with the ESS detector group suggest an approximate costing for such a detector of €1.45M for the 90° bank, and €0.80M for the horizontal bank. We propose that the secondary horizontal detector bank can be considered as an upgrade, adding an additional element of contingency should the need arise.

Neutron guide system: A conventional, curved guide of 170m length is estimated to cost in the region of €5.6M (this total includes an estimate of €1.53M for shielding and an upgrade to m=3 supermirrors of €0.94M)

Choppers: The ESPRESSO chopper system is relatively simple, requiring 4 choppers and the option for one of these to have a translatable position along the beam. The estimated cost for these is €0.88M

Instrument Infrastructure: The instrument hutch and controls are costed at €256k. In addition, the instrument will require motion control systems estimated at €101k

Sample Environment: The full SE budget includes the cost of a R&D programme to develop new designs dedicated to ESPRESSO. This latter R&D project includes 2 years of postdoctoral effort, and costs for consultancy, finite element analysis, prototyping and testing. Also included is the cost of a final suite of 5 pressure cells for use on the instrument.

Laser systems: Online combined fluorescence and Raman spectrometer (€60k) and laser heating (€44k)

Ancillary DAC laboratory: As pressure cells are likely to become activated during use and because frequent loading and reloading of cells is inevitable, it will be necessary to provide a support lab in the proximity of the instrument. In addition to the basic construction and conventional facilities, this laboratory would require several items of specialist equipment and general laboratory tools. The total cost is €371k

Personnel: Total manpower costs are €1.628M including lead scientist, engineering support and 2 years of postdoctoral effort on the SE R&D programme...

The total cost for the instrument is €12.164M (including a 10% contingency). Excluding the second detector bank and the upgrade to the supermirror coating, this cost would reduce to €10.721M (also including contingency).

The full budgetary analysis is given in Appendix M.

2. BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Boehler, R. et al. Large-volume diamond cells for neutron diffraction above 90GPa. *High Pressure Research* 33, 546-554 (2013).
2. Wu, J. J. et al. Magnetic and structural transitions of SrFe₂As₂ at high pressure and low temperature. *Scientific Reports* 4 (2014).
3. Ashcroft, N. W. Metallic Hydrogen - a High-Temperature Superconductor. *Physical Review Letters* 21, 1748-& (1968).
4. Cudazzo, P. et al. Ab initio description of high-temperature superconductivity in dense molecular hydrogen (vol 100, art no 257001, 2008). *Physical Review Letters* 101 (2008).
5. Howie, R. T., Guillaume, C. L., Scheler, T., Goncharov, A. F. & Gregoryanz, E. Mixed Molecular and Atomic Phase of Dense Hydrogen. *Physical Review Letters* 108 (2012).
6. Eremets, M. I. & Troyan, I. A. Conductive dense hydrogen. *Nature Materials* 10, 927-931 (2011).
7. Silvera, I. F. & Wijngaarden, R. J. New Low-Temperature Phase of Molecular Deuterium at Ultrahigh Pressure. *Physical Review Letters* 47, 39-42 (1981).
8. Goncharenko, I. & Loubeyre, P. Neutron and X-ray diffraction study of the broken symmetry phase transition in solid deuterium. *Nature* 435, 1206-1209 (2005).
9. Johnson, K. A. & Ashcroft, N. W. Structure and bandgap closure in dense hydrogen. *Nature* 403, 632-635 (2000).
10. Kohanoff, J., Scandolo, S., Chiarotti, G. L. & Tosatti, E. Solid molecular hydrogen: The broken symmetry phase. *Physical Review Letters* 78, 2783-2786 (1997).
11. Silvera, I. F. The Solid Molecular Hydrogens in the Condensed Phase - Fundamentals and Static Properties. *Reviews of Modern Physics* 52, 393-452 (1980).
12. Mao, H. K. et al. Synchrotron X-Ray-Diffraction Measurements of Single-Crystal Hydrogen to 26.5 Gigapascals. *Science* 239, 1131-1134 (1988).
13. Cavazzoni, C. et al. Superionic and metallic states of water and ammonia at giant planet conditions. *Science* 283, 44-46 (1999).
14. Goncharov, A. F. et al. Dynamic ionization of water under extreme conditions. *Physical Review Letters* 94 (2005).
15. Pickard, C. J. & Needs, R. J. Highly compressed ammonia forms an ionic crystal. *Nature Materials* 7, 775-779 (2008).
16. Guthrie, M. et al. Neutron diffraction observations of interstitial protons in dense ice. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110, 10552-10556 (2013).
17. Ashcroft, N. W. Hydrogen dominant metallic alloys: High temperature superconductors? *Physical Review Letters* 92 (2004).
18. Chen, X.-J. et al. Pressure-induced metallization of silane. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 105, 20-23 (2008).
19. Eremets, M. I., Trojan, I. A., Medvedev, S. A., Tse, J. S. & Yao, Y. Superconductivity in hydrogen dominant materials: Silane. *Science* 319, 1506-1509 (2008).
20. Gao, G. et al. High-pressure crystal structures and superconductivity of Stannane (SnH₄). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 107, 1317-1320 (2010).
21. Hanfland, M., Proctor, J. E., Guillaume, C. L., Degtyareva, O. & Gregoryanz, E. High-Pressure Synthesis, Amorphization, and Decomposition of Silane. *Physical Review Letters* 106 (2011).
22. Martinez-Canales, M. et al. Novel Structures and Superconductivity of Silane under Pressure. *Physical Review Letters* 102 (2009).
23. Sun, L., Ruoff, A. L., Zha, C.-S. & Stupian, G. High pressure studies on silane to 210 GPa at 300 K: optical evidence of an insulator-semiconductor transition. *Journal of Physics-Condensed Matter* 18, 8573-8580 (2006).
24. Szczesniak, R. & Durajski, A. P. The high-pressure superconductivity in SiH₄: The strong-coupling approach. *Solid State Communications* 172, 5-9 (2013).
25. Wei, Y. K. et al. Pressure induced metallization of SiH₄(H-2)(2) via first-principles calculations. *Computational Materials Science* 88, 116-123 (2014).
26. Yao, Y. & Klug, D. D. Silane plus molecular hydrogen as a possible pathway to metallic hydrogen. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 107, 20893-20898 (2010).
27. Zhang, C. et al. Superconductivity in Hydrogen-rich Material: GeH₄. *Journal of Superconductivity and Novel Magnetism* 23, 717-719 (2010).
28. Drozdov, A. P., Eremets, M. I. & Troyan, I. A. Conventional superconductivity at 190K at high pressures. *arXiv arXiv:1412.0460 [cond-mat.supr-con]* (2014).
29. Feng, J. et al. Structures and potential superconductivity in SiH₄ at high pressure: En route to "metallic hydrogen". *Physical Review Letters* 96 (2006).

30. Kim, D. Y. et al. Crystal structure of the pressure-induced metallic phase of SiH₄ from ab initio theory. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 105, 16454-16459 (2008).
31. Strobel, T. A. et al. High-pressure study of silane to 150 GPa. *Physical Review B* 83 (2011).
32. Degtyareva, O., Proctor, J. E., Guillaume, C. L., Gregoryanz, E. & Hanfland, M. Formation of transition metal hydrides at high pressures. *Solid State Communications* 149, 1583-1586 (2009).
33. Kim, D. Y., Scheicher, R. H., Pickard, C. J., Needs, R. J. & Ahuja, R. Predicted Formation of Superconducting Platinum-Hydride Crystals under Pressure in the Presence of Molecular Hydrogen. *Physical Review Letters* 107 (2011).
34. Szczesniak, R., Szczesniak, D. & Huras, K. M. Description of the superconducting state in the high-pressure fcc phase of platinum-hydride. *Physica Status Solidi B-Basic Solid State Physics* 251, 178-183 (2014).
35. Guillaume, C. L. et al. Cold melting and solid structures of dense lithium. *Nature Physics* 7, 211-214 (2011).
36. Loveday, J. S. & Nelmes, R. J. Ammonia monohydrate VI: A hydrogen-bonded molecular alloy. *Physical Review Letters* 83, 4329-4332 (1999).
37. Feng, J., Hennig, R. G., Ashcroft, N. W. & Hoffmann, R. Emergent reduction of electronic state dimensionality in dense ordered Li-Be alloys. *Nature* 451, 445-448 (2008).
38. Hermann, A., Ivanov, B. L., Ashcroft, N. W. & Hoffmann, R. LiBeB: A predicted phase with structural and electronic peculiarities. *Physical Review B* 86 (2012).
39. Loveday, J. S., Nelmes, R. J., Guthrie, M., Klug, D. D. & Tse, J. S. Transition from cage clathrate to filled ice: The structure of methane hydrate III. *Physical Review Letters* 87 (2001).
40. Vos, W. L., Finger, L. W., Hemley, R. J. & Mao, H. K. Novel H₂-H₂O Clathrates at High-Pressures. *Physical Review Letters* 71, 3150-3153 (1993).
41. Wright, J. P., Bell, A. M. T. & Attfield, J. P. Variable temperature powder neutron diffraction study of the Verwey transition in magnetite Fe₃O₄. *Solid State Sciences* 2, 747-753 (2000).
42. Kunes, J., Lukoyanov, A. V., Anisimov, V. I., Scalettar, R. T. & Pickett, W. E. Collapse of magnetic moment drives the Mott transition in MnO. *Nature Materials* 7, 198-202 (2008).
43. Rueff, J. P., Mattila, A., Badro, J., Vanko, G. & Shukla, A. Electronic properties of transition-metal oxides under high pressure revealed by x-ray emission spectroscopy. *Journal of Physics-Condensed Matter* 17, S717-S726 (2005).
44. Yoo, C. S. et al. First-order isostructural Mott transition in highly compressed MnO. *Physical Review Letters* 94 (2005).
45. Pasternak, M. P., Xu, W. M., Rozenberg, G. K. & Taylor, R. D. Electronic, magnetic and structural properties of the RFeO₃ antiferromagnetic-perovskites at very high pressures. *Perovskite Materials* 718, 15-24 (2002).
46. Greenberg, E. et al. Mott transition in CaFe₂O₄ at around 50 GPa. *Physical Review B* 88 (2013).
47. Greenberg, E. (2014).
48. Cohen, R. E., Mazin, I. I. & Isaak, D. G. Magnetic collapse in transition metal oxides at high pressure: Implications for the Earth. *Science* 275, 654-657 (1997).
49. Debessai, M. et al. Superconductivity under high pressure in the binary compound CaLi₂. *Physical Review B* 78 (2008).
50. Gao, L. et al. Superconductivity up to 164-K in HgBa₂Ca_{m-1}Cu_{m+2}Δ (M=1,2, and 3) under Quasi-Hydrostatic Pressures. *Physical Review B* 50, 4260-4263 (1994).
51. de la Cruz, C. et al. Magnetic order close to superconductivity in the iron-based layered LaO(1-x)F(x)FeAs systems. *Nature* 453, 899-902 (2008).
52. Huang, Q. et al. Neutron-Diffraction Measurements of Magnetic Order and a Structural Transition in the Parent BaFe₂As₂ Compound of FeAs-Based High-Temperature Superconductors. *Physical Review Letters* 101 (2008).
53. Baldini, M., Di Castro, D., Cestelli-Guidi, M., Garcia, J. & Postorino, P. Phase-separated states in high-pressure LaMn_{1-x}Ga_xO₃ manganites. *Physical Review B* 80 (2009).
54. Malavasi, L. et al. High pressure behavior of Ga-doped LaMnO₃: a combined X-ray diffraction and optical spectroscopy study. *Journal of Materials Chemistry* 20, 1304-1311 (2010).
55. Baldini, M., Struzhkin, V. V., Goncharov, A. F., Postorino, P. & Mao, W. L. Persistence of Jahn-Teller Distortion up to the Insulator to Metal Transition in LaMnO₃. *Physical Review Letters* 106 (2011).
56. Baldini, M. et al. Pressure-induced tuning of a magnetic phase separation in Nd_{0.53}Sr_{0.47}MnO₃. *Physical Review B* 86 (2012).
57. Baldini, M. et al. Pressure induced magnetic phase separation in La_{0.75}Ca_{0.25}MnO₃ manganite. *Journal of Physics-Condensed Matter* 24 (2012).
58. Cheng, J.-G. et al. Anomalous perovskite PbRuO₃ stabilized under high pressure. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110, 20003-20007 (2013).
59. Lin, Y. et al. Amorphous Diamond: A High-Pressure Superhard Carbon Allotrope. *Physical Review Letters* 107 (2011).

60. Zhang, L. et al. Catalyst-free synthesis of transparent, mesoporous diamond monoliths from periodic mesoporous carbon CMK-8. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 107, 13593-13596 (2010).
61. Fitzgibbons, T. C. et al. Benzene-derived carbon nanothreads. *Nature Materials* (2014).
62. Zeng, Q. S. et al. Substitutional alloy of Ce and Al. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 106, 2515-2518 (2009).
63. Zeng, Q. S. et al. Long-Range Topological Order in Metallic Glass. *Science* 332, 1404-1406 (2011).
64. Nelmes, R. J. et al. Annealed high-density amorphous ice under pressure. *Nature Physics* 2, 414-418 (2006).
65. Meade, C., Hemley, R. J. & Mao, H. K. High-Pressure X-Ray-Diffraction of SiO₂ Glass. *Physical Review Letters* 69, 1387-1390 (1992).
66. Guthrie, M. et al. Formation and structure of a dense octahedral glass. *Physical Review Letters* 93 (2004).
67. Salmon, P. S. et al. Density-driven structural transformations in network forming glasses: a high-pressure neutron diffraction study of GeO₂ glass up to 17.5 GPa. *Journal of Physics-Condensed Matter* 24 (2012).
68. Drewitt, J. W. E. et al. Structure of GeO₂ glass at pressures up to 8.6 GPa. *Physical Review B* 81 (2010).
69. Vepřek, S. The search for novel, superhard materials. *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology A* 17, 2401-2420 (1999).
70. Irifune, T., Kurio, A., Sakamoto, S., Inoue, T. & Sumiya, H. Ultrahard polycrystalline diamond from graphite (vol 421, pg 599, 2003). *Nature* 421, 806-806 (2003).
71. Redfern, S. A. T., Henderson, C. M. B., Wood, B. J., Harrison, R. J. & Knight, K. S. Determination of olivine cooling rates from metal-cation ordering. *Nature* 381, 407-409 (1996).
72. Mao, Z. et al. (Fe, Al)-bearing post-perovskite in the Earth's lower mantle. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 403, 157-165 (2014).
73. Pearson, D. G. et al. Hydrous mantle transition zone indicated by ringwoodite included within diamond. *Nature* 507, 221-+ (2014).
74. Sanloup, C. et al. Structural change in molten basalt at deep mantle conditions. *Nature* 503, 104-+ (2013).
75. Duffy, T. S. Earth Science Probing the Core's Light Elements. *Nature* 479, 480-481 (2011).
76. Zhang, L. et al. Disproportionation of (Mg,Fe)SiO₃ perovskite in Earth's deep lower mantle. *Science* 344, 877-882 (2014).
77. Pearson, D. G. et al. Hydrous mantle transition zone indicated by ringwoodite included within diamond. *Nature* 507, 221-224 (2014).
78. Pamato, M. G. et al. Lower-mantle water reservoir implied by the extreme stability of a hydrous aluminosilicate. *Nature Geosci* 8, 75-79 (2015).
79. Nishi, M. et al. Stability of hydrous silicate at high pressures and water transport to the deep lower mantle. *Nature Geosci* 7, 224-227 (2014).
80. Redfern, S. A. T. et al. Octahedral cation ordering in olivine at high temperature. II: an in situ neutron powder diffraction study on synthetic MgFeSiO₄ (Fa₅₀). *Physics and Chemistry of Minerals* 27, 630-637 (2000).
81. Murakami, M., Hirose, K., Kawamura, K., Sata, N. & Ohishi, Y. Post-Perovskite Phase Transition in MgSiO₃. *Science* 304, 855-858 (2004).
82. Andrault, D. et al. Solid-liquid iron partitioning in Earth's deep mantle. *Nature* 487, 354-+ (2012).
83. Marshall, W. G.
84. Tulk, C. A.
85. Arima, H. et al. Designing PLANET: Neutron beamline for high-pressure material science at J-PARC. *International Conference on High Pressure Science and Technology, Joint Airapt-22 and Hpcj-50* 215 (2010).
86. Stahn, J. et al. in *Status report on the WP2 of the Swiss-Danish instrumentation work packages for the ESS* (2012).
87. Bertelsen, M. (University of Copenhagen, 2014).
88. Chou, I. M., Blank, J. G., Goncharov, A. F., Mao, H. K. & Hemley, R. J. In situ observations of a high-pressure phase of H₂O ice. *Science* 281, 809-812 (1998).
89. Ninet, S., Datchi, F. & Saitta, A. M. Proton Disorder and Superionicity in Hot Dense Ammonia Ice. *Physical Review Letters* 108 (2012).
90. Ninet, S. et al. Experimental and theoretical evidence for an ionic crystal of ammonia at high pressure. *Physical Review B* 89 (2014).
91. Kolesnikov, A., Kutcherov, V. G. & Goncharov, A. F. Methane-derived hydrocarbons produced under upper-mantle conditions. *Nature Geoscience* 2, 566-570 (2009).
92. Maynard-Casely, H. E. et al. The distorted close-packed crystal structure of methane A. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 133, 064504 (2010).
93. Strobel, T. A., Somayazulu, M. & Hemley, R. J. Novel Pressure-Induced Interactions in Silane-Hydrogen. *Physical Review Letters* 103 (2009).

94. Martinez-Canales, M., Bergara, A., Feng, J. & Grochala, W. Pressure induced metallization of Germane. *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* 67, 2095-2099 (2006).
95. Li, Z., Yu, W. & Jin, C. First-principles calculation on phase stability and metallization in GeH₄ under pressure. *Solid State Communications* 143, 353-357 (2007).
96. Gao, G. et al. Superconducting High Pressure Phase of Germane. *Physical Review Letters* 101, 107002 (2008).
97. Strobel, T. A., Chen, X.-J., Somayazulu, M. & Hemley, R. J. Vibrational dynamics, intermolecular interactions, and compound formation in GeH₄-H₂ under pressure. *Journal of Chemical Physics* 133 (2010).
98. Zhong, G. et al. Superconductivity in GeH₄(H₂)₂ above 220 GPa high-pressure. *Physica B-Condensed Matter* 410, 90-92 (2013).
99. Tse, J. S., Yao, Y. & Tanaka, K. Novel Superconductivity in Metallic SnH under High Pressure. *Physical Review Letters* 98, 117004 (2007).
100. Somayazulu, M. et al. Pressure-induced bonding and compound formation in xenon-hydrogen solids. *Nature Chemistry* 2, 50-53 (2010).
101. Somayazulu, M., Gramsch, S., Mao, H. K. & Hemley, R. High pressure-high temperature reactions in xenon-chlorine system. *Materials Research at High Pressure* 987, 127-132 (2007).
102. Fabbiani, F. P. A. & Pulham, C. R. High-pressure studies of pharmaceutical compounds and energetic materials. *Chemical Society Reviews* 35, 932-942 (2006).
103. Fabbiani, F. P. A. et al. Pressure-induced formation of a solvate of paracetamol. *Chemical Communications*, 3004-3005 (2003).
104. Millar, D. I. A. et al. Pressure-cooking of explosives-the crystal structure of epsilon-RDX as determined by X-ray and neutron diffraction. *Chemical Communications* 46, 5662-5664 (2010).
105. Millar, D. I. A., Barry, C., Marshall, W. G. & Pulham, C. R. Structural characterization of sodium azide and sodium bifluoride at high pressures. *Zeitschrift Fur Kristallographie* 229, 259-275 (2014).
106. Hunter, S. et al. Combined Experimental and Computational Hydrostatic Compression Study of Crystalline Ammonium Perchlorate. *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 115, 18782-18788 (2011).
107. Millar, D. I. A. et al. Putting the squeeze on energetic materials-structural characterisation of a high-pressure phase of CL-20. *Crystengcomm* 12, 2524-2527 (2010).
108. Prescimone, A. et al. Pressure-Driven Orbital Reorientations and Coordination-Sphere Reconstructions in [CuF₂(H₂O)₂(pyz)]. *Angewandte Chemie-International Edition* 51, 7490-7494 (2012).
109. Prescimone, A. et al. [Mn-6] under pressure: A combined crystallographic and magnetic study. *Angewandte Chemie-International Edition* 47, 2828-2831 (2008).
110. Graham, A. J. et al. Stabilization of Scandium Terephthalate MOFs against Reversible Amorphization and Structural Phase Transition by Guest Uptake at Extreme Pressure. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 136, 8606-8613 (2014).
111. Moggach, S. A., Bennett, T. D. & Cheetham, A. K. The Effect of Pressure on ZIF-8: Increasing Pore Size with Pressure and the Formation of a High-Pressure Phase at 1.47 GPa. *Angewandte Chemie-International Edition* 48, 7087-7089 (2009).
112. Arnold, P. L. et al. Strongly coupled binuclear uranium-oxo complexes from uranyl oxo rearrangement and reductive silylation. *Nature Chemistry* 4, 221-227 (2012).
113. Arnold, P. L. et al. Uranyl oxo activation and functionalization by metal cation coordination. *Nature Chemistry* 2, 1056-1061 (2010).
114. Wilson, R. M., Loveday, J. S., Nelmes, R. J., Klotz, S. & Marshall, W. G. Attenuation Corrections for the Paris-Edinburgh Cell. *Nuclear Instruments & Methods in Physics Research Section a-Accelerators Spectrometers Detectors and Associated Equipment* 354, 145-148 (1995).
115. Loveday, J. S., McMahon, M. I. & Nelmes, R. J. The Effect of Diffraction by the Diamonds of a Diamond-Anvil Cell on Single-Crystal Sample Intensities. *Journal of Applied Crystallography* 23, 392-396 (1990).
116. Guthrie, M., Boehler, R., Molaison, J. J., dos Santos, A. M. & Tulk, C. A. Powder neutron diffraction with diamond anvil cells. *Amer. Cryst. Assoc. Trans. Ser.* 44, 149-169 (2013).
117. Boehler, R. (2013).

3. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Explanation of abbreviation
HP	High Pressure
HPT	High Pressure and Temperature
SC	Superconductor
CMR	Colossal magnetoresistance
SE	Sample Environment
SSS	Science Support Systems
DAC	Diamond Anvil Cell
Q	Momentum transfer
PDF	Pair Distribution Function
PSC	Pulse shaping chopper

4. APPENDICES

Appendix A Survey of synchrotron publications

Here we have attempted to survey the impact that a high-pressure neutron diffractometer would have on science that is currently being carried out at major synchrotron facilities in Europe (the ESRF) and the USA (the APS). The starting point was to select a subset of peer-reviewed publications from each facility in the field of high-pressure science. A slightly different approach was required for each as the various user offices employ different search engines. For the ESRF, it was possible to conduct a full-text search of publications. This was done using the search terms "pressure" and "gpa", which yielded 54 publications spanning a time range of 2013-15. At the APS only title searches were possible and here, titles with the word "pressure" in them were selected, yielding 164 publications after manual purging of non high-pressure papers.

Starting with these lists, titles and abstracts were studied and it was noted whether two key attributes of neutron scattering, namely sensitivity to light elements and magnetic structure, would contribute to the scientific case being made. In addition, pressure and temperature range was noted to determine whether it exceeds present capability. Finally, a significant percentage of the APS papers were clearly technical as opposed to scientific. These were excluded from the final totals.

The resulting statistics are summarised here:

	Number of publications surveyed	Period	Percentage benefitting from neutron	Percentage requiring ESPRESSO
<i>ESRF</i>	<i>54</i>	<i>2013-2015</i>	<i>44.4%</i>	<i>29.6%</i>
<i>APS</i>	<i>160</i>	<i>1998-2015</i>	<i>38.1%</i>	<i>23.7%</i>

We also found the need for neutron contrast was slightly higher than for magnetic structure information. Of the APS publications benefitting from neutrons, 62% would do so from light-atom contrast and 40% from ability to measure long-range magnetic order. For the ESRF, the equivalent numbers were 62% and 50% respectively (note the sum of percentages exceed 100% due to some experiments benefitting from both of these advantages of neutrons).

Appendix B Hydrogen and the dense molecular ices

Hydrogen we have simulated diffraction patterns for several of the candidate structures for phase II, the "broken symmetry phase" (shown in Figure 20). It's clear that data over a narrow bandwidth

would be sufficient to resolve the difference between these structures. Beyond this, key structural information, such as the H-H (or D-D) distance could be extracted from Bragg peaks down to 0.6-0.7 Å.

Figure 20 Simulated diffraction patterns for several proposed structures¹⁰ of phase II of hydrogen at 60 GPa. The lower symmetry of these structures, relative to hcp, could lead to splitting of the diffraction peaks. However, no information is at present available on the unit cell under these conditions of pressure, and these data are calculated with an ideal pseudo-hcp unit cell.

Ice Although the phase diagram of ice becomes relatively simple above 2 GPa, much remains to be explained. The behaviour of ice VII and its proton-ordering transition to ice VIII changes above 15 GPa. In addition the Raman signal changes radically in the 20-50 GPa range. There is at present no clear structural basis for these changes and ESPRESSO will allow this to be investigated. The high temperature capability will also be crucial. There are longstanding predictions of a superionic phase above (40 GPa and 1000 C) and light-scattering studies appear to confirm the existence of a triple point in the melting curve¹⁴. Access to high-grade diffraction data will allow the structural basis of this change to be explored for the first time. Studies of the liquid structure will explore how liquid-water changes with pressure – it is predicted to become a 'normal' liquid at high pressure. An ambitious target is a study of the transition to centred ice X⁸⁸ which starts at ~80 GPa and is complete by ~120 GPa, measurements of the proton extent – as determined by the anisotropic hydrogen ADPs -- would provide valuable benchmarks for theoretical studies.

Ammonia also has a superionic phase at high pressures and temperatures¹³ whose structure is reported to be path dependent. ESPRESSO's small sample and high-T capability will enable this to be addressed. Ammonia is also pressure ionized above 60 GPa at moderate temperatures of 700K⁸⁹ and above 100 GPa at room temperature where IR and x-ray studies interpret the ionic phase as a mixture of two phases which persists over at least 90 GPa⁹⁰. Almost certainly this wide 'coexistence' range indicates some hydrogen substructure that x-ray's cannot see. ESPRESSO will address this.

Methane is important both as a constituent of planets and as the simplest alkane. Its HPHT behaviour and whether it dissociates into hydrogen and diamond or polymerises to form longer chain alkanes is crucial to models of Uranus and Neptune and to tests of the behaviour of volatiles in the Earth's mantle⁹¹. The basic thermodynamic data (like the density) needed to settle these issues rests on structures which are poorly known. Structures also provide insight into how non-hydrogen bonded systems interact at high density. At present full structural data is only available to 12 GPa. ESPRESSO will extend this knowledge to 100 GPa. The crystal structure of methane A⁹² illustrates some of the complexity of high pressure systems. It has 21 molecules in the unit cell, which has trigonal symmetry

and relatively large lattice parameters. The diffraction pattern (Figure 21) at 5 GPa shows a longest d-spacing of 5.577Å, requiring wavelengths of 7.887Å at 90 degrees. Meanwhile $\delta d/d$ of at least 0.6% to resolve overlapping reflections.

Figure 21 Simulated diffraction pattern of methane A at 5 GPa illustrating the need for both long d-spacing reflections and high diffraction resolution. Inset shows overlapping peaks.

The **binary** and **ternary** mixtures of methane water and ammonia are also crucial to modelling of the outer solar system. For example the possible ionisation of ammonia-water (see below) is directly relevant to Uranus and Neptune's magnetic fields and methane-water (see below) is crucial to the understanding of how methane is circulated between planetary interiors and atmospheres. Almost nothing is known about methane ammonia and the methane-water-ammonia ternary. ESPRESSO's high P and T capability will enable characterisation of a 'synthetic' Uranus for the first time.

Appendix C Superconducting hydrogen-rich materials

Perhaps most attention has focused on the lightest group 14 hydride (but for methane) **silane**. The first predictions of its stable structures under pressure came in 2006, suggesting a series of transitions from 4 to 6 to 8 coordinate Si beginning above 25 GPa, and with metallization occurring below 100 GPa. Most intriguingly, exceedingly high superconducting transition temperatures T_c (as high as 166K) were predicted²⁹. In the meantime, several other theoretical groups have proposed a range of stable structures^{22,30}. Interestingly, experimental studies indicated a much lower pressure of metallization of around 30 GPa¹⁸ with a subsequent experimental claim of superconductivity at 96 GPa¹⁹ turning out to be controversial³². The highest-pressure structural measurements to date, using x-ray diffraction, made the surprising discovery of pressure-induced amorphisation at 60 GPa, with subsequent recrystallisation and polymerisation at 90 GPa^{21,31}. With such complex behaviour, there is clearly an urgent need for neutron diffraction to unravel the structural details of this complex material.

Beyond, pure silane, there have been fascinating spin-off discoveries in studies of the **mixed silane:hydrogen** system. In these, Strobel *et al*³³ reported the formation of stable structure with an extremely unusual anti-correlated pressure dependence of the H₂ vibron indicating unexpected attractive interactions between SiH₄ and H₂. Without neutron diffraction, even the stoichiometry of the system is uncertain, however a possible formula of SiH₄(H₂)₂ has been claimed on the basis of optical volumetric measurements. Any detailed information on the structure of a material that is 89% hydrogen would be unobtainable without neutron diffraction on deuterated analogues. At much higher pressure, but still accessible to ESPRESSO, the mixture has been calculated to become metallic below 120 GPa²⁶. This suggests that a tantalising possibility of a structural study, by neutron diffraction, of analogue of metallic hydrogen.

[Germane](#) has also been theoretically predicted by different groups to metallize at 70 GPa⁹⁴, or ~ 50 GPa⁹⁵ both within the expected range of ESPRESSO. At higher pressures, it has been calculated⁹⁶ to gradually dissociate up to 196 GPa a process that ESPRESSO could again shine light on. Like silane, the germane:hydrogen system has also been found to lead to stable compound formation at intermediate pressures⁹⁷ and comparative studies of these and the silane compounds on ESPRESSO would yield detailed information on the nature of their unusual bonding schemes. At higher pressures, the system may also superconduct⁹⁸ and ESPRESSO could explore changes in the structural framework on the approach to this phase.

Also a gas at ambient conditions, [stannane](#) has been studied using first principles calculations⁹⁹ with the prediction of a novel layered structure intercalated with H₂ units stable above 70 GPa. These pressures are not accessible to current neutron probes so, correspondingly, the claim that it will exhibit extremely short H...H contact of ~0.84 Å has never been tested. Intense interest in this phase has been triggered because of the prediction that it will exhibit high temperature superconducting temperature of 80 K. Neutron diffraction data from ESPRESSO is the only route to definitively determine the full structure in this system.

High pressure seems to have a way of conferring serendipity and the intense focus on these hydrogen rich materials has had some fascinating spin off phenomena. For example, Eremets et al's claim of direct experimental observation of superconductivity in silane¹⁹ may actually have been attributable to superconductivity in a hydride formed from his platinum electrodes³²!. At ambient conditions, platinum is highly-unreactive and the formation of a high pressure hydride was completely unexpected and has now itself generated substantial interest in Pt-hydride itself³²⁻³⁴. Neutron diffraction is perhaps the only technique that can reveal the structure of this material and even basic characteristics, such as stoichiometry, are inaccessible to any other probe. The high pressures of 70 GPa required to form the stable hydride could only be accessed using the dedicated micro-beams available on ESPRESSO.

Another spin off that arose from attempts to metallise so-called "dirty hydrogen", that is a system with a very high atomic density of hydrogen, diluted by a secondary, "contaminant" phase. One of the systems considered was to mix hydrogen with noble gases. Surprisingly, and entirely unexpectedly, and a whole new class of Van-der-Waals compounds was found in the xenon-hydrogen system^{100,101}. Indirect estimates of stoichiometry reveal two distinct compounds (formed at 4.9 and 5.4 GPa) with formulae Xe(H₂)₇ and Xe(H₂)₈. X-ray diffraction indicates that the Xe atoms are distributed as dimers, suggesting the formation of bonds between these noble atoms; it is not known how hydrogen might act to stabilise these unusual pairs. Not only is neutron diffraction the definitive tool to study the structural nature of these extremely hydrogen-dense compounds, but their stability range (extending to 220 GPa) means that the interactions can be studied across a huge distribution of densities.

Appendix D Low and ambient pressure applications of ESPRESSO

The utility of ESPRESSO goes far beyond extreme conditions research. In particular, at low pressures, where sample volume can be maximised, the ability to trade flux for resolution will enable detailed crystallographic studies. One example where this will enable new science is in studies of [Polymorphism in complex molecular materials](#) High diffraction resolution is key to understanding pressure-induced polymorphism, which is of crucial importance for a wide range of molecular materials that include pharmaceuticals, energetic materials, pigments and optoelectronics¹⁰². For example, within the [pharmaceutical industry](#), the identification of polymorphic forms of drug compounds is of particular importance because two polymorphs of the same drug compound may have very different physical properties that affect bioavailability or processibility¹⁰³ (e.g. tableting). In addition, different polymorphs of a drug compound can be patented. Similar remarks apply to solvates and hydrates of pharmaceutical compounds. Of course, such systems are hydrogen rich and neutron characterization will make a powerful scientific contribution to our understanding of structure (for which H-bonding plays a critical role) and its relation to functionality. [Energetic materials](#) (explosives and propellants) also exhibit polymorphism and characterising this, under extremes of pressure and temperature, are key to understanding the processes of detonation and deflagration¹⁰⁴⁻¹⁰⁷. Neutron techniques are key due to their sensitivity to light atoms and for avoiding the radiation damage from synchrotrons. Still further systems that can be specifically tailored by high pressures include [molecular magnets](#)^{108,109}, [porous](#)

materials^{110,111}, small-molecule activation catalysts (such as H₂ and CO₂) and materials used in the processing of radioactive wastes. Of these latter, very little work has been done at high pressure although ambient pressure work, hints at the clear importance and possibilities for this^{112,113}.

ESPRESSO's optimisation for neutron-diffraction studies of microsamples (in the 10's of microgram range) within containers adds critical capability to the ESS suite even for science even for studies at ambient conditions. In particular, although NMX will also be optimized for very small samples, its high wavelength cut-off precludes the atomic-level information available to ESPRESSO. One field to benefit from this capability is the structural characterization of highly radioactive or toxic materials. By minimizing both sample volume and using containment, such hazards can be greatly minimized if not entirely negated. For example, beryllium-containing materials (which are limited to time-weighted average levels of 2µg m⁻³ in the EU) could be studied on ESPRESSO with appropriate containment. This provides a completely new capability as Be and important compounds such as BeH₂ are all but invisible to x-ray techniques. Meanwhile another application is the ability to study heterogeneous materials where the material could be scanned sequentially through a beam potentially as small as 50µm. In other cases, it may only be possible to synthesize the materials of interest in miniscule amounts. Where neutron information is essential, ESPRESSO would provide a unique World-wide capability to study microscopic samples.

Appendix E Guide calculations

In initial stages of design, ESPRESSO was envisaged as viewing the 3cm thermal pancake moderator. The guide calculations described below compared three guide possibilities:

- 1) A straight conventional guide
- 2) A curved conventional guide, and
- 3) A "Selene"-type guide

It was concluded that a curved conventional guide was the ideal solution to deliver ESPRESSO's technical requirements.

Subsequently, the decision was made to introduce the spectral switch into the design, allowing an option to view the cold source in order to greatly enhance longer wavelength performance. At this stage, guide_bot was again used to obtain the optimal solution across the full wavelength range of the new design. At this stage of calculation, the current baseline design of butterfly moderator was incorporated in the calculations.

The thermal 3cm pancake moderator

Two sets of guide calculations have been carried out. The first has compared conventional straight and curved guides with a selene concept guide using guide_bot. The second calculation is a simulation of a straight conventional guide using standard McStas. Here, the results of the guide_bot simulations are presented, followed by a document describing the McStas calculations. (note in both documents, ESPRESSO is referred to by its working title of "MicroN").

Guide_bot straight conventional guide, thermal source

micron_conventional_6

ESE - ESE_1Hsize1 - E(maxlength=40) S E(maxlength=40)

Sample size: Horizontal=0.001m, Vertical=0.001m, Divergence requirement: Horizontal=0.7deg, Vertical= 0.7deg, Sample distance =2m

Intensity on sample of 100 emitted = 8504010 (no divergence limit) 28346.6992 (width divergence limits)

Intensity near sample of 100 emitted = 8504010 (no divergence limit)

micron_conventional_6

ESKSE - ESKSE_2Hsize1 - E(maxlength=40) S E(maxlength=40)

Sample size: Horizontal=0.001m, Vertical=0.001m, Divergence requirement: Horizontal=0.7deg, Vertical= 0.7deg, Sample distance =2m

Intensity on sample of 100 emitted = 7802330 (no divergence limit) 26007.8008 (width divergence limits)

Intensity near sample of 100 emitted = 7802330 (no divergence limit)

C.3 Guide_bot Selene-type guide

micron_focusing_3

Selene - Selene_2Vdiv1 - Selene

Sample size: Horizontal=0.002m, Vertical=0.002m, Divergence requirement: Horizontal=0.15deg, Vertical= 0.15deg, Sample distance =0m

Intensity on sample of 100 emitted = 1102190 (no divergence limit) 3621.97 (width divergence limits)

Intensity near sample of 100 emitted = 1102200 (no divergence limit)

Neutron transport with a conventional guide (microN)

J.P. de Vicente
Consorcio ESS-Bilbao

Prof. P. Henry
European Spallation Source ESS AB

(Dated: January 14, 2015)

Insert abstract here
here Insert abstract here Insert abstract here Insert abstract here

I. INTRODUCTION

ESS as a long-pulse neutron source will require long instruments in order to reach good spectral resolution at detector positions. On the other hand, the high pressure diffractometer proposal, microN, extends the neutron temperature of interest up to the epithermal range. Thermal neutrons are difficult to transport. Hence neutron guides will play an important role during the optimization process in order to transport neutrons from the shortest wavelength, 0.5 Å. The instrument also will penalise neutron rays with high divergence at sample position. Divergences below 0.5° will be considered as useful rays. But the rest will be unwanted.

In this study, we are looking for the best case scenario for the flux and divergence criteria at sample position that we have using a conventional guide type. Simulations were carried out with McStas^{1,2} and the iFit tool³.

II. INSTRUMENT MODEL

The starting point for the model is the general parameters fixed by the Scientific Case, see Table I.

TABLE I. microN general parameters

Pancake moderator	12x3 cm ²
Moderator-guide distance	2.0 m (max. 5° sector)
Max. divergence	±0.5°
Fightpath	170 m
Max. guide section	40x40 cm ² (chopper window)
Guide-sample distance	2.0 m
Sample size	< 650x650 μm ²
Guide exit	<3.5x3.5 cm ²

ESS themal source is taken from tables given by K. Andersen and M. Bertelsen. Figure ?? shows the neutron mean brilliance emerging from the 3 cm pancake moderator.

As a conventional guide we used a straight elliptic one since it presents the best performance in almost all as-

pects⁴. Guide is elliptical at both planes, horizontal and

FIG. 1. Neutron mean brilliance at the 3 cm pancake moderator. Data from Ken Andersen and Mads Bertelsen.

vertical. The *Elliptic_guide_gravity* component for McStas was employed. At this stage no curving guide to avoid the line of sight was considered. Gravitational effects were taken into account in the simulations. Sample should be at least 2 m distance from the guide exit. This gap allows exchangeable optics to be installed.

In order to achieve the divergence criteria a set of slits are in the way of neutrons between the guide exit and the sample. These slits prevent divergences higher than 0.5° to hit the sample. The first slit is close to the guide exit. The last one is the 0.5 mm diameter circle at 5 mm from sample position (sample slit). For the simulations we do not need to put any further slits into the model, but it is clear that the actual instrument will need to have further slits, that are defined by the gravity component of the longest wavelength in the band used for the experimental set-up (P. Henry advice). Sample space in the diamond anvil cell should be no more than 650 μm in order to avoid contact with the steel supports. This is the maximum size for the sample since it will become smaller as pressure is applied. Nevertheless the sample slit defines a umbra region of 414 μm where the sample is fully illuminated (see Figure 2). We will focus on the flux over the umbra region. The objective of this focusing system (defined by the Scientific Case) was to maximize the umbra region while minimizing the penumbra one.

FIG. 2. Focusing system at sample position. The sample slit avoids divergences higher than 0.5° to hit the sample region defined by the umbra

The distance from the guide to the sample slit ($\approx 2\text{m}$) and the divergence criteria define the maximum size of the exit of the guide. A simple trigonometric calculation yields a maximum of $3.5 \times 3.5 \text{ cm}^2$.

Maximum guide section (minor axis of the ellipse) is taken as 40 cm in order to accommodate beam choppers and other size restrictions⁶.

III. OPTIMIZATION PROCESS

The Liouville's theorem asserts that the phase-space distribution function is constant along the trajectories of the system⁵. In terms of neutron optics, brilliance (neutrons/s/cm²/Å/sr) is the phase-space of the beam. Against the theorem there will be a brilliance reduction along the transport due to the neutron leaks. Leaks come from the non-ideal reflection of the guide coating and from those neutrons hitting the guide with a grazing angle higher than the critical one. Therefore brilliance transfer (B) from the entrance of the guide to the exit, as $B = \Psi_2/\Psi_1$, can be a useful measurement for performance of the guide⁴, where Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 are the brilliance at the entrance and the exit of the guide, respectively.

Thus the optimization process will try to maximize the brilliance transfer for the useful neutrons (B_u) while minimize the brilliance transfer for the background neutrons (B_b). Note that in terms of divergence criteria, useful neutrons are those with a divergence lower than 0.5° . Background neutrons are the rest.

The elliptic guide geometry is defined by eight free parameters, four for the horizontal plane and four for the vertical one. The eight input parameters of the *Elliptic_guide_gravity* McStas component are the distances from 1st and 2nd focal points to the guide entrance and to the exit respectively, the guide length, and the dimen-

sions of the minor axis. But the restrictions given by the Scientific Cases (previous section) state the maximum for the exit of the guide ($< 3.5 \times 3.5 \text{ cm}^2$). Hence in order to delimit the search of the optimized values in agreement with these restrictions we need to find the relationship between these parameters, i.e. the relation between the distances to the focal points and the entrance and the exit of the guide. Trigonometric calculations over the geometry of a ellipse bring the expressions given by Eq. 1. It states the relationship between the focal distances and the guide sections.

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{H_e}{2}\right)^2 &= b^2 \left(1 - \frac{(L - d_1 + d_2)^2}{(L + d_1 + d_2)^2 + 4b^2}\right) \\ \left(\frac{H_s}{2}\right)^2 &= b^2 \left(1 - \frac{(L + d_1 - d_2)^2}{(L + d_1 + d_2)^2 + 4b^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where H_e is the size of the guide entrance, H_s is the size of the guide exit, b is the size of the guide at midpoint (minor axis of the ellipse), L is the guide length, d_1 is the distance from the 1st focal point to the guide entrance, and d_2 is the distance from the 2nd focal point to the guide exit. So finding d_1 and d_2 from the system given by Eq. 1 we have the input parameters for the model, i.e. $d_1(H_e, H_s, L, b)$, $d_2(H_e, H_s, L, b)$, L and b . We can make the change of variables $R = -d_1 + d_2$ and $S = d_1 + d_2$. Then finding the variables R and S from the system 1 we have Eq. 2 and Eq. 3.

$$R = \frac{1}{H_s^2 - H_e^2} \left(2L \sqrt{(H_e^2 - 4b^2)H_s^2 - 4b^2H_e^2 + 16b^4 + L(H_s^2 + H_e^2 - 8b^2)} \right) \quad (2)$$

FIG. 3. Brilliance transfer of useful and background neutrons from the entry to the exit of the guide.

$$S = \frac{\pm 2b}{H_s^2 - H_e^2} \left(-8L^2 \sqrt{(H_e^2 - 4b^2)(H_s^2 - 4b^2)} - (H_s^2 - H_e^2)^2 + L^2(32b^2 - 4H_e^2 - 4H_s^2) \right) - L \quad (3)$$

From $d_1 = (S - R)/2$ and $d_2 = (S + R)/2$ we have the input parameters for the model. The particle swarm algorithm⁸ was used for the multidimension space optimization with the iFit tool³. The optimization process tracked the size of the guide entrance between 1 and 10 cm, the minor axis of the ellipse between 5 and 40 cm, and the size of the guide exit between 1 and 3.5 cm, for both horizontal and vertical planes.

IV. RESULTS

As previous section exposed, optimization process was focused to maximize the brilliance transfer of useful neutrons along the guide, i.e. $\uparrow B_u$. The guide geometry meeting this optimization is listed by Table II and labeled as "opt1". Figure 3 shows the brilliance transfer of neutrons from the entry of the guide to the exit for "opt1". As the geometry is optimized for transfer the useful neutrons (divergence lower than 0.5°), the useful brilliance transfer tends to the unity as wavelength grows. Nevertheless there is a drop about 4 \AA . This drop is probably due to an increase on the neutron divergence then becoming background neutrons.

The brilliance transfer of background neutrons (B_b) is also more effective with the wavelength as expected. But background neutrons (divergence greater than 0.5°) contaminate the sample. Hence B_b must be minimized. This criterion was taken into account in the optimization process also through the ratio useful/background bril-

liance transfer, B_u/B_b , that it is the new variable to optimize. The new optimized geometry is shown in Table II also. It is labeled as "opt2". Figure 3 shows how "opt2" decrease the brilliance transfer of background neutrons respect the "opt1" geometry but at the cost of decrease the brilliance transfer of the useful neutrons also. For the sake of reduce the background neutrons, henceforth we select "opt2" as the optimized geometry for the guide.

TABLE II. Optimal elliptic guide geometries (values in cm)

	entry width	entry height	mid. width	mid. height	exit width	exit height
opt1	7.50	6.83	35.08	26.72	2.74	2.03
opt2	6.64	5.80	30.15	28.90	2.25	1.00

Figure 4 shows the brilliance transfer as function of divergence from the entry of the guide to the exit. Lower wavelengths are difficult to transfer as expected. But it seems that some neutrons rays increase their divergences along the guide. As a result the brilliance transfer exceeds the unity.

The flux as function of wavelength and divergence at sample position can be observed in Figure 5. The monitors are limited to the umbra region defined by the previous Figure 2. No background neutrons are recorded at the sample position. Even the divergence criteria is less than 0.35°

Figures 6-a) and-b) represent position sensitive monitors at sample position. It can be seen how the useful neutrons (a) are around of a region of $4w \times 2h \text{ cm}^2$, while the background neutrons (b) are around a grater space except in a central region where the sample should be housed. This central region should be free of background neutrons theoretically.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

My special thanks to Paul Henry for his advice for how to manage the present study. Peter Willendrup and

Emmanuel Farhi for their help on the iFit optimization

FIG. 4. Brilliance transfer as function of the divergence for some wavelength ranges

process. Kaspar Klenø for his advice on the brilliance transfer calculation. ESS DMSC Computing Centre and i2Basque programme for their computing supports.

-
- ¹ K. Lefmann and K. Nielsen, *Neutron News* **vol.10**, pag.20 (1999).
² P. Willendrup, E. Farhi and K. Lefmann, *Physica B* **vol.350**, pag.735 (2004).
³ E. Farhi, Y. Debab and P. Willendrup, *J. Neut. Res.* **vol.17**, (2013).
⁴ K.H. Klenø, K. Lieutenant, K.H. Andersen, and K. Lefmann, *Nuclear Instrument and Methods A.* **vol.696**,

- pag.75-84(2012).
⁵ L.D. Landau and E.M. Lifshitz, *Statistical Physics*, 3rd ed. **vol.1**, (1951).
⁶ K.H. Klenø *Simulating Neutron Guides for the European Spallation Source*, Master thesis in physics (2008).
⁷ H. Arima et al, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **215**, (2010).
⁸ J. Kennedy and R.C. Eberhart, *Proc. IEEE Conf. on Neural Networks, IV*, Piscataway, NJ, pag.1942-1948(1995).

FIG. 5. Flux as function of wavelength and divergence at sample position. Sample position defined by the focussing system. The umbra region is recorded.

FIG. 6. Position sensitive monitors at sample position for a) useful neutrons (divergence lower than 0.5°) and b) background neutrons (divergence greater than 0.5°).

Curved guide optimised for switchable source, Butterfly moderator

In these final calculations, the current baseline 3cm butterfly moderator was included and the guide design required to optimise across the full wavelength range of the switchable instrument.

Appendix F Attenuation of difference cell construction materials

Regardless of design, the neutron beam must always pass through the body of the pressure cell in order to reach the sample. Particularly at longer wavelengths, this can lead to severe attenuation. In addition to neutronic properties, there are also stringent limits on mechanical properties (in particular, hardness) of HP anvils. The traditional neutron anvil material, tungsten carbide (WC), has been in use since the 1960's, but has a high neutron absorption. Another material is sintered polycrystalline diamond (PCD), but the use of cobalt as a binder in the sintering process introduces both absorption and activation issues. As much of the ESPRESSO science case depends on longer wavelengths, up to 6.5Å, it is important to ensure that suitable materials exist that will allow adequate transmission of the neutron beam. Luckily, recent developments have led to the availability of new ultra-hard materials with excellent neutron transmission properties including zirconium toughened alumina (ZTA) and both poly-nano-crystalline (PNCD) and single crystal diamond (SCD), the latter forms of diamond being formed from pure carbon.

Figure 22 Transmission curves for 5mm of 5 different pressure cell materials

Figure 22 shows simple linear attenuation calculations (ignoring Bragg edge structure) for 5mm (likely a maximum amount of material required) of these candidate construction materials. The conventional materials - tungsten carbide (WC) and sintered polycrystalline diamond (PCD), which has a cobalt binder - show severe attenuation of the beam at the maximal wavelength of 6.5Å. However, the ZTA material shows quite reasonable transmissions of > 80%. Meanwhile, the pure carbon forms of diamond are perfectly transparent. As discussed further in Section 1.2.9 these latter materials have already been demonstrated as, feasible although optimal designs have likely not yet been realised. In

particular, the availability of ~1 cm³ blocks of PNCD and ~0.2 cm³ single-crystal diamond (via new CVD technologies) looks set to revolutionise pressure cell design. Both new diamond materials have already been tested in high pressure applications and will be fully exploited in ESPRESSO pressure cell designs. We can, therefore, safely conclude that a maximum wavelength of 6.5 Å for ESPRESSO is quite plausible and, indeed, higher wavelengths still may be accessible, depending on signal-to-background levels.

A final note on attenuation is that – unavoidably – transmission of the beam through any crystalline material will be subject to dips in intensity due to Bragg scattering. These introduce complexity to data normalisation procedures. However, this is entirely tractable and there is now almost over two decades of experience with employing semi-empirical corrections for polycrystalline¹¹⁴⁾ and single-crystal diamond anvils¹¹⁵⁾.

Appendix G Flux comparison between ESPRESSO, SNAP and PEARL.

The flux and resolution of ESPRESSO are calculated using a back-of-the-envelope approach, and compared to SNAP at SNS and PEARL at ISIS. At equal resolution, the flux on ESPRESSO is greater than both the other instruments for wavelengths above about 0.7 Å. In the core wavelength region between 1 Å and 2.5 Å, the flux on ESPRESSO exceeds that on SNAP by about an order of magnitude and on PEARL by more than two orders of magnitude. An upgrade to ISIS TS1 and installation of a guide on PEARL would result in a flux increase on PEARL by about a factor of 8, leaving it about a factor of ten below SNAP in flux.

By using a pulse-shaping chopper to determine the instrumental resolution, ESPRESSO will be able to tune its resolution between about 0.1% and 1%, while matching the resolution contributions from the pulse width and divergence, so as to maximize the flux on sample at all times. In addition to its flux advantage, ESPRESSO will thus also benefit from an unprecedented flexibility in tuning resolution versus flux in order to match the requirements of each individual experiment.

Introduction

ESPRESSO will have access to both thermal and cold segments of the ESS 3cm butterfly moderator. In order to access both sources without compromise in flux, it will feature a spectral switch, and be able to operate in either a thermal or cold mode.

The performance of ESPRESSO will be compared to SNAP at SNS and PEARL at ISIS. SNAP views the decoupled poisoned hydrogen moderator at SNS and PEARL views the liquid methane moderator at ISIS TS1. Figure 28 shows a comparison of the source brightnesses. It is sometimes assumed that instrument performance at a pulsed source scales very simply with the peak brightness. That is not the case for a long-pulse source, in which the instruments are specifically designed to also benefit from the very high time-average brightness.

ESPRESSO will be a very long instrument - about 170 m from source to detectors, allowing a wavelength band of 1.8 Å and a very flexible trade-off between resolution and flux by varying the opening time of a pulse-shaping chopper, placed close to the target monolith wall.

Flux Calculation

In order to calculate the flux on the sample, we start from the time-average brightness B of the various sources shown in Figure 28. These curves then need to be multiplied by the source solid angle $\Delta\Omega$ which is transported to the sample by the guide system, and also by the instrument duty cycle R , i.e. the fraction of the source pulse width which is transported to the instrument, as expressed in equation 1 below.

$$\Phi = B \times \Delta\Omega \times R \tag{1}$$

The source solid angle transported to the sample in Eq. (1) is given by

$$\Delta\Omega = BT \times \Delta\theta_H \times \Delta\theta_V \tag{2}$$

where BT is the wavelength-dependent brilliance transfer and $\Delta\theta_H$ and $\Delta\theta_V$ are the horizontal and vertical divergence intervals transported to the sample. As SNAP and PEARL have no fixed guide before the sample, their divergence intervals are given by the angle subtended by the moderator, viewed from the sample position, which is roughly 0.2° (FWHM of a triangular distribution) with a BT of 1. The ESPRESSO guide system will transport an adjustable divergence of up to ±0.7°, as provided by the guide system shown in Fig. [refer to Mads's figure in the main text showing the guide geometry]. For calculation of the flux on sample on ESPRESSO we use the BT shown in Fig. [refer to Mads's figure in the main text showing the wavelength-dependent brilliance transfer] and horizontal and vertical divergence intervals of 0.2° (full width of a top hat = FWHM of a triangle), for consistency with the SNAP and PEARL calculations.

For PEARL and SNAP, the duty cycle R in Eq. (1) is unity, as the full pulse width is used. For ESPRESSO, however, the pulse width can be freely chosen out of the 2.86 ms duration of the full pulse,

Figure 23 Brightness curves comparing peak and time average flux for the ESS baseline 3cm butterfly moderator with those viewed by SNAP and PEARL.

using a series of pulse-shaping choppers. This represents an additional flexibility for ESPRESSO, which can give a substantial performance boost.

In order to achieve a resolution which is approximately constant as a function of d-spacing, the pulse width should be proportional to wavelength. A good approximation to this is achieved by the poisoning and decoupled of the moderators viewed by PEARL and VISION. To achieve a similar effect at the long-pulse source of the ESS, we will employ a pair of choppers in a "double-blind" configuration, as illustrated in Figure 24 below.

Figure 24 Principle Principle of the double-blind chopper system: use the trailing edge of the first chopper coinciding in time with the leading edge of the second chopper, in order to extract a wavelength-proportional pulse width Δt at the choppers and τ at the source.

The use of such a double-blind chopper system allows the extraction of a neutron pulse with a duration which is proportional to the neutron wavelength. It is currently foreseen that the second chopper will be moveable in order to freely select a chopper distance ΔL between 0.20 and 2.0 m [check values for consistency with the main text]. The extracted pulse width at the source is given by

$$\tau[\text{ms}] = \Delta L[\text{m}] \times \frac{\lambda[\text{\AA}]}{3.956[\text{m/ms/\AA}]} \times \frac{L_1 + L_2}{L_2} \tag{3}$$

The duty cycle used for calculating the flux in Eq. (1) is then given by

$$R = \tau / 2.857\text{ms} \tag{4}$$

where R is capped at 1, in case the calculated value of τ exceeds the available source pulse width. For the case of ESPRESSO, τ does not exceed 2.857ms within the calculated wavelength range.

The flux at the sample calculated using Eq. (1) is shown in Fig. 27 below.

Figure 25 Calculated flux at sample for ESPRESSO, SNAP and PEARL

The resulting calculated flux is shown in Figure 31 where it is seen that in the thermal regime, ESPRESSO will provide a flux at sample that is higher than that of SNAP at wavelengths above about 0.75 Å, reaching about an order of magnitude improvement over SNAP in the critical wavelength range around 1.5 Å. The ESPRESSO flux is between 1 and 2 orders of magnitude higher than that of PEARL over the full wavelength range. Also shown in the figure is the flux which can be expected from an upgraded PEARL, benefiting from a TS1 upgrade and a supermirror neutron guide.

An upgrade to the TS1 moderator system is expected to result in an increase in brightness of the methane moderator of a factor 2-3 [3], which has been averaged as a factor of 2.5 in the calculation for the upgraded PEARL. Installation of a supermirror guide on PEARL will result in a similar source solid angle being transported to the sample as on ESPRESSO, resulting in a further factor of 3. The curve labelled "upgraded PEARL flux" has been obtained by simply multiplying the "PEARL flux" curve by a factor of 8. ISIS power upgrades have not been considered; any increases in the accelerator power at ISIS will likely not be compatible with the increased radiation damage to the methane moderator, which would have to be replaced by a water or hydrogen moderator, resulting in a very different resolution and flux.

For longer wavelength regimes, where the cold source is viewed, the gain over SNAP and PEARL is still further enhanced: rapidly reaching a factor of 20 over SNAP and then increasing roughly linearly until it reaches x70 around 6.5 Å.

Resolution calculation

The resolution of the instrument is determined by the moderator pulse width Δt and the beam divergence $\Delta\theta$, as given by equation 2 below:

$$\Delta d = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial d}{\partial \lambda} \Delta \lambda\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial d}{\partial \theta} \Delta \theta\right)^2}$$

$$\text{where } \frac{\partial d}{\partial \lambda} \Delta \lambda = d \frac{\Delta t}{t} \text{ and } \frac{\partial d}{\partial \theta} \Delta \theta = d \cot \theta \Delta \theta \quad (5)$$

Table 1 summarises the instrumental resolution on SNAP, PEARL and ESPRESSO.

	SNAP		PEARL		ESPRESSO		
L(mod-det)	15.5m		13.6m		170m		
Divergence	0.35°		0.20°		0.35°		
Wavelength	1 Å	2 Å	1 Å	2 Å	1 Å	2 Å	Flux calc.
Pulse width	12µs	22µs	14µs	45µs	10 -1000µs	10 -1000µs	147µs/Å
Δd/d at 2θ=90°	0.68%	0.67%	0.54%	0.74%	0.61 -2.41%	0.61- 1.31%	0.70%
Δd/d at 2θ=135°	0.40%	0.38%	0.43%	0.67%	0.25 -2.34%	0.25 -1.19%	0.43%

The first term in the resolution calculation of Eq. (5) comes from the pulse width, which for SNAP and PEARL is given by the viewed moderator, as shown in Figure 30. For ESPRESSO, however, the pulse width

Figure 26 Moderator pulse width of the SNS decoupled poisoned water and ISIS TS1 methane moderators as a function of neutron wavelength, Also shown is the opening time of the ESPRESSO pulse-shaping chopper, scaled down by a factor of 10, for the resolution conditions used for the flux calculation.

can be freely chosen out of the 2.86 ms duration of the full pulse, using a pulse-shaping chopper, which is why a range of pulse widths is given for ESPRESSO in Table 1. This represents an additional flexibility for ESPRESSO, which can give a substantial performance boost.

The ISIS and SNS moderator pulse widths have been extracted from the data in Figure 28 as follows: The peak brightness B_{pk} is defined as the maximum instantaneous brightness during a pulse - it takes no

account of the repetition rate. The time-average brightness B_{ave} is the instantaneous brightness averaged over an integer number of pulses (including the dead time between pulses). It is in the same units as the peak brightness. It should be given by the peak brightness adjusted for the time structure: $B_{ave} \approx B_{pk} \times w/T = B_{pk} \times w \times f$ where w is the time-width of the pulse, $T=1/f$ is the repetition period, and f is the repetition rate.

The SNS repetition rate is 60Hz, while for the case of TS1 at ISIS, the repetition rate to use for evaluating the pulse widths is 40Hz, rather than 50Hz when, as one pulse in five is transported to TS2. The pulse widths calculated in this way for the SNAP and PEARL moderators are shown in Figure 30.

By using a double-blind pulse-shaping chopper pair at the ESS, ESPRESSO will extract a pulse width that is proportional to wavelength. The pulse width for ESPRESSO is given by the solid line in Figure 30, which is chosen to give approximately the same resolution at the 90° and 135° detector banks as on SNAP and PEARL, as shown in the last column of Table 1.

Figure 27 Variation of flux on ESPRESSO, SNAP and PEARL as a function of resolution. The incident divergence was varied between 0.1° and 0.2° for PEARL and up to 0.5° for SNAP and ESPRESSO. For ESPRESSO the pulse-shaping chopper was set to select a pulse-width half-way between the pulse-widths required to match the divergence-contribution to the resolution at 90° and 135° detector angle.

On ESPRESSO, unlike on any short-pulse instrument, it is possible to tune the instrumental resolution to the sample, depending on the range of d-spacings and symmetry of the unit cell, allowing the user to maximize the flux by degrading resolution in a controlled way. On short-pulse instruments, such as SNAP and PEARL, this is primarily done by adjusting the divergence impinging on the sample. However, this only varies one of the two terms contributing to the resolution, as seen in Equation 6. Since the pulse width is given by the moderator and hence cannot be changed during the experiment, varying the divergence quickly results in a highly unoptimised configuration in which either the pulse width dominates the resolution (when the divergence is reduced) or the divergence dominates (when it is increased).

This limits the best achievable resolution and also limits the flux that can be obtained by relaxing resolution. To maximize flux, the two terms in Equation 6 should be kept approximately equal, which can only be achieved on SNAP or PEARL for one particular choice of resolution, but is straightforwardly done on ESPRESSO at any resolution by varying the divergence and the pulse length together. The resulting variation of flux with resolution is shown in Figure 32 for a wavelength of 1.41 \AA , chosen to correspond to a d-spacing of 1 \AA at a detector angle of 90° .

Discussion

The flux comparison in Figure 31 is not entirely straightforward, because it does not take into account (1) the rather different wavelength ranges offered on the three instruments and (2) the added flexibility from the pulse-shaping chopper system on ESPRESSO which allows the user to reach resolutions as high as 0.1% or fluxes at the sample as much as $10\times$ higher than shown in Figure 31, by degrading resolution.

The source repetition rate and instrument lengths of SNAP and PEARL combine to give them wavelength bandwidths of 4.3 \AA and 5.8 \AA respectively, as compared to 1.8 \AA on ESPRESSO. In order to cover the same wavelength range on ESPRESSO, you would have to run the chopper system in pulse-skipping mode, using only one pulse in 3 or 4, effectively reducing the flux on sample by a factor of 3 or 4. However, there will be many cases where a bandwidth of 3.4 \AA or 1.8 \AA is enough, in which case you would change your chopper speeds and recover 50% or 100% of the full flux shown in Figure 31.

The second term in the resolution calculation of Eq. (6) comes from the divergence impinging on the sample. SNAP has a removable parabolic guide that is used with diamond cell samples, increasing the divergence beyond the 0.2° corresponding to the direct view of the moderator. Similarly, on ESPRESSO, a larger divergence of $\pm 0.7^\circ$ is transported by the guide system, allowing a flexible range of divergence on the sample to be chosen using pin-holes. Since PEARL has no guide, the divergence transported to the sample is simply given by the moderator size, viewed from the sample position, providing a maximum divergence of $0.2^\circ \times 0.2^\circ$ (FWHM of a triangular distribution), corresponding to a moderator width and height of 10 cm and a small sample placed at a distance of 12.8 m.

The pulse-width and divergence contributions to the resolution should be matched in order to maximize the flux for a given resolution. This can be freely done on ESPRESSO, resulting in the flux vs resolution curves shown in Fig. 28, while on SNAP and PEARL, only the divergence can be adjusted, as the pulse width is fixed by the moderator. Fig. 28 shows the much greater range of flux and resolution which can be selected on ESPRESSO, due to this additional flexibility.

It is seen in Figure 28 that being able to tune the pulse width to match the divergence provides a substantially greater range of resolutions to choose from, as well as ensuring that the pulse-width and divergence contributions to the resolution are always matched, such that the flux on sample is maximized for every choice of resolution. The resolution on ESPRESSO can thus straightforwardly be varied between about 0.1% and 1% with a gain in flux on the sample of about two orders of magnitude from relaxing the resolution. The resolution on PEARL is dominated by the moderator line width, resulting in almost no change in resolution as the divergence is varied, while the range of resolutions available on SNAP is about half that of ESPRESSO. The calculations shown in Figure 32 demonstrate that any given resolution, ESPRESSO will outperform SNAP by about an order of magnitude.

To conclude, the flux on ESPRESSO is up to an order of magnitude higher than that of its closest competitor SNAP in the thermal range between 0.75 Å and ~2.5 Å. Above ~2.5 Å, when cold source is viewed, the gains rapidly increase to factors of 20-70 over SNAP. Meanwhile, SNAP starts to outperform ESPRESSO in terms of flux for wavelengths shorter than about 0.75 Å, but here must struggle against increasing backgrounds that should be mitigated on ESPRESSO by the long flight path. Compared to PEARL, the flux on ESPRESSO is 1-1.5 orders of magnitude higher in the thermal regime and a full 3 orders of magnitude higher at 5 Å with ESPRESSO in "cold" mode. If the TS1 moderator system is upgraded and PEARL simultaneously receives a guide upgrade, then the upgraded PEARL will outperform ESPRESSO for wavelengths shorter than about 0.4 Å, while ESPRESSO will still provide more than a factor of 10 higher performance for the critical wavelength range around 1 Å and have far superior performance at longer wavelengths. In addition to the flux advantages, ESPRESSO has much more freedom to trade resolution for flux than both SNAP and PEARL.

References

- [1] High Power Target Station Design as of 7/31/02, Erik Iverson (2002), <http://neutrons.ornl.gov/instruments/support/moderators/HPTS-sct/>
- [2] Goran Skoro and Rob Bewley, private communication, October 2014
- [3] Systematic performance study of common neutron guide geometries, K. Hewitt Klenø et al., Nucl Instr. Meth. A 696, 75 (2012)
- [4] Goran Skoro, TS1 upgrade presentation, ICANS-XXI workshop, Mito, Japan, October (2014)

Appendix H Pixel size and estimated maximal count-rates

The most intense flux impinging on the ESPRESSO detector bank is expected to be due to single-crystal reflections from the diamond anvils. Not only are such anvils several orders of magnitude larger in volume than the sample, but their high symmetry and single-crystal character acts to concentrate the scattered radiation into very localised volumes of Q-space.

In a diamond-anvil cell, the 100 axis is close aligned to the load axis of the cell. In the (most commonly used) 90° geometry of ESPRESSO, this means that the incident neutron beam will also travel along the 100 axis. The strongest Bragg reflection is expected to be the 111 and, in the 90° geometry, the Bragg condition will be satisfied for 4 of the 8 symmetrically equivalent 111-type reflections at a wavelength of ~2.4 Å (depending on the exact orientation of the crystal to the beam). The approximate physical size of the single-crystal peak on the detector is estimated by the linear dimensions of the illuminated part of the diamond, viewed from the detector, broadened by the divergence. The most intense flux corresponds to the smallest peak sizes, which will occur for the lowest envisaged divergences of around ±0.25°. This will give a spot size of ~ 8x8 mm².

We can estimate the maximum expected count rate due to a 111 reflection, in the nth pixel, R_n(111) with the following equation:

$$R_n(111) = \text{sample size (cm}^2\text{)} * \text{flux on sample (n/s/cm}^2\text{/Å)} * \text{scattering fraction} * \dots \\ \text{fraction of intensity in 111-type reflections} * \dots \\ 1/(\text{multiplicity of 111}) * \text{peak width 111 in wavelength} * \dots \\ \text{detector efficiency}$$

Our guide simulations for a 500 μm diameter sample (Figure 13) show a maximum flux of 7.0×10^6 n/s/ \AA . Here we consider a maximum sample size of 1mm diameter, increasing area by a factor of 4 and giving a count rate of 2.8×10^7 . In addition, we assume a scattering fraction of <5% and estimate that < 20% of the total scattered radiation goes into the 111 reflections, giving Bragg peaks with <0.05 \AA total width. Finally, the detector efficiency at 2.4 \AA is unlikely to exceed $\sim 50\%$. Substituting these values into the equation above, we get $R_p(111) = 2.8 \times 10^7 * 0.05 * 0.2 * 0.25 * 0.05 * 0.5 = 1.75 \times 10^3$ n/s. It is possible that reflections from each of the two diamond anvils could overlap, doubling this rate to 3.5×10^3 n/s. Such a reflection would be distributed over ~ 7.1 pixels, given a maximum count-rate per channel of 4.9×10^2 n/s.

Appendix I Comparison of ESPRESSO powder data with SNAP and PEARL

Figure 33 (Left) indicates typical signal-to-background levels for a strong scattering system (ice VII) inside a DAC measured in SNAP with the parabolic focusing optic (Sample mass was around 50 μg its diameter 650 μm and thickness 160 μm)¹¹⁶. Tests indicated that the dominant source of the background was due to γ -rays emanating from the collimation. The background subtracted data (Right) show peaks that are substantially broadened by the increased divergence, leading to peak overlaps at low d-spacing, despite the high symmetry unit cell ($pn\bar{3}m$).

The closest comparable datasets for ESPRESSO are those measured on SNAP. Typical sample sizes are in line with those proposed for ESPRESSO and Figure 40 shows an example dataset for 50 μm of ice VII measured inside a diamond cell on SNAP. Salient features of the patterns shown are the relatively large background, due to γ -rays originating from the local cell collimation and cell body, relatively broad

Figure 34 Diffraction from around 5 μg of ice VII at pressures up to 94 GPa (each data set ~ 10 minutes) showing the 110, 111 and 220 Bragg peaks. The letters H and B indicate residual steel peaks from the bcc and hcp phase of iron. These data both illustrate the potential of high pressure neutron diffraction, while underscoring the need for a next-generation instrument.

diffraction peaks and weak contaminant peaks from the steel gasket.

Measurements have also been made on SNAP, where the sample size was dropped by almost a further factor of 10, samples have been driven to almost a 94 GPa (Figure 35).

As discussed in the main proposal, there is substantial scope to improve on these, already impressive, data. Extensive testing on SNAP has shown that the primary background source is due to γ radiation (a known issue for the Anger cameras used on SNAP). By using alternative detector technologies, this background source will be greatly reduced. In addition, secondary background from fast neutrons will be greatly reduced by the much longer flight path on ESPRESSO: 170m vs 15m corresponding to a reduction of over 2 orders of magnitude.

At comparable resolutions, ESPRESSO will have around 10 times more flux than SNAP. Due to its inherent flexibility, this flux could be “exchanged” for resolution. Correspondingly, *at comparable flux* the $\delta d/d$ resolution could be improved by a factor of 5 relative to SNAP.

Appendix J Double-aperture calculations.

The detailed geometry of a double aperture system is described in Figure 36 from which the key relations between aperture size and location and beam dimensions are readily calculated.

For a given beam umbra of radius r_u , it can be seen that the divergence $\delta\theta$ depends only on the location (x_1) and radius (r_1) of Aperture 1:

$$\delta\theta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{r_1 - r_u}{x_1}\right) \approx \left(\frac{r_1 - r_u}{x_1}\right)$$

From Figure 36 it can be seen that for any given position of the second aperture (x_2), its optimum radius (r_2) is then fixed by the divergence:

$$r_2 \approx r_u + x_2\delta\theta$$

It follows that, for a given divergence, the extent of penumbra p is then controlled solely by the location of Aperture 2. This then defines the total extent of the beam r_{beam} :

$$r_{beam} = r_u + x_2\delta\theta + x_2\left(\frac{r_1+r_u+x_2\delta\theta}{x_1-x_2}\right) \tag{2}$$

which is just the sum of the umbra and penumbra. It follows from Eqn (2) that

$$p = x_2\delta\theta + x_2\left(\frac{r_1+r_u+x_2\delta\theta}{x_1-x_2}\right) \tag{3}$$

The optimum signal is obtained by maximizing the integrated intensity of the beam given by the area, I_{int} under the beam profile shown in the insert to Figure 36. The best possible case is obtained when the penumbra is zero and when the umbra radius is equal to the sample radius r_{sam} .

Figure 36 Pinhole aperture geometry described in a reference frame where the x-axis is parallel and coincident with the beam, pointing upstream towards the moderator and where the z-axis is vertical. Cylindrical symmetry is assumed and the sample is placed at the origin. The edge of the upstream aperture (1) is at a distance of x_1 from the sample and has a radius of r_1 , while the downstream aperture (2) is at a distance x_2 from the sample and has a radius of r_2 . The divergence, $\delta\theta$ and the angle of the penumbra, $\delta\phi$ are shown, giving rise to an umbra at the sample position with radius r_u and a penumbra of extent p . The insert shows the beam profile as a function of z at the sample position.

We can then define a beam “filling fraction”, f referenced to this case (noting that the corresponding $f=1$ can only be obtained with zero penumbra i.e. $x_2=0$):

$$f = \frac{2r_u + p}{2r_{sam}}$$

Appendix K Pressure cell R&D project.

The proposed work here builds on a concerted and well-funded effort to expand the capabilities of neutron DACs (NDACs) conducted from 2010-2014, funded by the US DOE and based on the SNAP diffractometer at the SNS. Main proposer Guthrie and co-proposer Boehler led this effort. In particular, Dr. Boehler is a recognised world expert in DAC design, laser-heating and HP spectroscopy with a career in HP spanning over 4 decades. This project delivered new cells (Figure 37) that allowed refineable neutron diffraction datasets up to 43 GPa¹⁶ and quantitative diffraction intensities up to 94 GPa¹.

Although the SNAP effort acts as a clear demonstration of the technical feasibility of NDACs it is also instructive on how the technique can be greatly optimised when combined with ESPRESSO instrumentation concepts. There is great scope for increased sample volume and improved stability through improved anvil support, use of new CVD diamond material and culets geometries optimised by finite element analysis. Another important consideration is diffraction aperture, which is minimal for existing designs, but would be optimised to match ESPRESSO’s detector geometry. Finally, improvement

Figure 37 Evolution of DAC cells used for neutron diffraction on SNAP. From left to right, the panoramic cell (ca 2001), the 'minibar' cell (ca 2013) which reached 94 GPa and the 'DCO' cell (ca 2014). All cells are compatible with existing gas loaders and use completely new designs of seats that support single-crystal diamond anvils with culets up to 1.5mm to forces exceeding 10 tonnes.

(particularly in mechanisation) of incident and diffracted beam collimators would be developed as part of the ESPRESSO sample environment plan.

A key material that we will exploit in the design of these new cells is CVD diamond material. Due to remarkable advances in the last 5 years, it is now possible to affordably purchase artificial single-crystal CVD material in cylinders with diameters up to 7mm x 5mm tall. Preliminary testing conducted by Guthrie and Boehler has shown that this material has mechanical strength at least equalling that of natural material. Moreover, work on SNAP using this material has clearly illustrated the enormous advantages of single-crystal diamond from the perspective of neutron diffraction: negligible attenuation in addition to clean and localised background signal.

Our development strategy will focus on increasing the volume of existing large-volume DAC designs (with proven capability for neutron diffraction^{16,116}), while increasing diffraction aperture, by optimising anvil support. In addition, laser ablation technologies will be explored as a means to shape profiles into the diamond culets as a way to further increase volume. For even larger volumes, preliminary concept designs exist to create a support “diamond piston cylinder”¹¹⁷.

The R&D program has the following goals:

- Optimise sample volume for a given pressure
- Maximise scattering aperture
- Create dedicated low-temperature cells with minimal mass

The first of these tasks will require development of new anvils. In addition to CVD diamond, we will explore the possibilities offered by poly-nano-crystalline diamond and ceramics such as ZTA. The

parameters to be explored are anvils size, support type (conical vs flat vs tensile) support materials (PCD vs WC vs steel). The strategy requires an iteration of a design, finite-element modelling and testing cycle.

The second two tasks require new cell designs. Existing designs are able to support a load of 10 metric tonnes, which is adequate for the majority of needs on ESPRESSO. However, the diffraction aperture of the cell is currently far too small to take advantage of the full detector complement lowering both count-rate and Q-range. The R&D effort required here, therefore, will focus on increasing the scattering aperture. As this necessarily requires reducing the stability of the cell, the result is likely a spectrum of several devices, optimised for say 2,5 and 10 tonnes.

By expanding the range of cells available, the scientific capability of the beamline will be maximised. A key example is that the lower capacity/mass variants will enable work at unprecedentedly low temperatures that are critical for studies of correlated electronic systems. Meanwhile, the largest capacity cells are vital for reaching the highest possible pressures.

A full 3 years period of development is envisaged to realise all of the goals of the project.

Appendix L Diamond Attenuation Correction

In the standard ESPRESSO 90° geometry, the beam must traverse a diamond anvil in order to reach the beam. Bragg reflections from the diamond introduce dips in the transmitted spectrum that affect the measured intensities. Investigations on SNAP found that the dip width and intensities were strongly pressure dependent. The former is a result of lattice strain, which then affects the latter by reducing extinction. A substantial development effort quantified this effect and developed a correction that can be implemented on-the-fly during beamtime. The details are given in the following extract from a draft manuscript in preparation.

The SNAP diamond transmission correction

The diamond transmission correction consists of the following steps:

- 1) For each sample dataset, also measure a transmission spectrum $T_{tot}^{meas} \equiv T_{tot}^{meas}(TOF)$
- 2) Create a model of the total transmission ($T_{tot}^{mod} \equiv T_{tot}^{mod}(\lambda)$) based on the individual calculated transmission through diamond 1 (upstream) T_{UB1}^{mod} and diamond 2 (downstream) T_{UB2}^{mod} . The model uses the known crystal structure of diamond with their orientations determined by fitting UB matrices to the diffraction spots measured in the 90 degree diffraction detectors
- 3) Refine the model to match the measured transmission to obtain the best fit to the data.
- 4) Output separately the model transmission from the upstream diamond $T_{UB1}^{mod}(\lambda)$
- 5) "Focus" $T_{UB1}^{mod}(\lambda)$ to give $T_{UB1}^{mod}(d)$. This is done using the same focusing routine (including same mask, and therefore same 2θ weighting as seen by the data.
- 6) This gives a final correction function that the data are divided by to correct for upstream diamond transmission effects.

Experimental data

The correction was developed using a test series of measurements taken on SNAP in October 2013. The loading details were 1.5mm diamond culets, with D2O ice VII loaded into T301 steel gaskets with initial ID ~600um. A panoramic cell was used with a membrane load driver. A decoupled collimator was used with a diameter of 600um. The datasets were:

Run	Sample	Hydraulic load (bar)	Force (Tonnes)	Sample pressure (GPa)
13115	D ₂ O	25	1.3	3.9
13116	D ₂ O	60	3.1	20.1
13146	D ₂ O	68.4	3.6	22.6
13148	D ₂ O	90	4.7	33.3
13149	Vanadium	0		

13150	Empty cell	0		
-------	------------	---	--	--

For each dataset, the diffraction detectors were both set at 90 degrees, and a downstream transmission detector was positioned immediately after the cell. This set-up is comparable to the PNAS datasets.

Step 1: measuring the transmission spectrum

A detector is positioned downstream of the DAC and a transmission dataset is collected simultaneously with the diffraction measurement. Then the cell is removed and a second dataset collected with (as close as possible) identical shielding and with the same collimation, using a kinetic repositioning system. For each of these measurements a *second* dataset was taken where the beam was blocked upstream of the collimator to give an estimate of the background. The raw data for the low pressure run 13115 are shown in Figure 38.

Figure 38 (A) Measured transmission data as a function of ToF both with and without the cell in place. The background signal for each of these measurements is also shown (all data are normalized to proton charge). The dips in measured intensity due to diamond diffraction are clearly visible. Bragg edges from upstream beam components at ~9500 and ~11000 us remain when the cell is removed. In (B) the backgrounds have been subtracted indicating that diamond attenuation is negligible outside of the

The transmission through the two diamonds is taken to be the ratio of the 'with cell' and 'without cell' measurements (after backgrounds are subtracted from each). In this ratio, wavelength-dependent factors such as the detector efficiency, incident flux profile and transmission through upstream windows cancels, leaving only the transmission due to the two diamond anvils. The final transmission is shown in Figure 2, here errors in the original transmission measurements have been propagated.

Figure 39 (A) Final transmission measurement due to two diamond anvils under a load of 1.3 tonnes with counting errors shown. This measurement shows that at the particular ToF (or wavelength) corresponding to a diamond "dip" as more than 80% of the beam has been removed. (B) shows effect of strain on the diamond dip intensities. The largest effect is seen between the first two load points at 1.3 and 3.1 tonnes: there is a notable increase in peak width and position and, for longest wavelength dip (corresponding to 111-type diamond reflections, see below) a substantial increase in dip intensity. Beyond this load, further smaller increases in the 111 dip intensity are seen.

Step 2: modelling the transmission spectrum

The beam reaching the sample has travelled through the upstream diamond and, therefore will have some dip structure imposed on it. However, the transmission measurements shown in Figure 39 show the total transmission from both upstream and downstream diamonds. In order to deconvolve these two components, it's necessary to build a model of the individual dip structure due to both diamonds.

Here, the basic assumption is that the intensity of a dip is exactly proportional to the intensity of the corresponding Bragg reflection(s). Bragg reflections (and dips) occur when the Bragg criteria is satisfied, which depends both on the wavelength of the incident beam and the angular orientation of the diamond crystal lattice relative to the beam. On SNAP, the diffraction detectors are always able to sample a subset of diamond Bragg reflections, and these can be used to determine the (3x3) orientation matrix of the diamonds, UB. For any reflection with miller indices h,k,l, the coordinates in Q space of the corresponding reflection are given by operating on the vector (h,k,l) using the UB matrix:

$$\overline{UB}(h, k, l) = \begin{pmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \\ Q_z \end{pmatrix} = \overline{Q_{hkl}}$$

The corresponding wavelength λ_{hkl} of the Bragg reflection is then given by the magnitude of the Q-vector:

$$\lambda_{hkl} = \frac{2\pi}{|\overline{Q_{hkl}}|}$$

It was quickly determined that imprecision in the UB determination, due to a finite pixel size $\sim 0.5^\circ$ and relatively low sampling of reflections was $\sim 1^\circ$. In order to take account of this, 3 "setting" angles α, β and γ were introduced to allow for adjusting the orientation of the diamond lattice in the beam. In addition to errors in the setting angles, it is also necessary to consider the effect of the load on the diamond lattice parameter, which can compress measurably. In order to take account of this in the model, a multiplicative scale factor δ is introduced to correct the wavelength of a dip, such that

$$\lambda_{hkl} \rightarrow \delta \lambda_{hkl}.$$

In our model, the dip corresponding to reflection h,k,l is approximated by a Gaussian function, centred on λ_{hkl} . The width of the Gaussian, σ is constrained to have a quadratic dependence on wavelength, such that $\sigma(\lambda) = \sigma_1 \lambda + \sigma_2 \lambda^2$. Finally, the initial values of the area of the Gaussians are taken to be the negative of the square of the calculated structure factors $|F_{hkl}^{calc}|^2$. These are then scaled

by an arbitrary multiplier A_{hkl} that is constrained to be the same for each set of equivalent reflections (e.g. $A_{111} = A_{\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1}}$ etc). Thus, the approach is akin to a model weighted LeBail fit to a powder diffraction pattern. The transmission complete spectrum for a given diamond with orientation matrix UB, T_{UB}^{mod} is then given by :

$$T_{UB}^{mod} = 1 - B_{UB} \sum_{h,k,l} A_{hkl} |F_{hkl}^{calc}|^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(\lambda - \lambda_{hkl})^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$$

It is possible to constrain all A_{hkl} to be identical for each diamond in this case, B_{UB} is a scale factor for the second diamond relative to the first, allowing for slight differences in diamond thickness and, therefore total attenuation. Alternatively, A_{hkl} can be different for each diamond in which case, B_{UB} is set equal to one and ignored. To sample dips to sufficiently small values of λ for the SNAP 90° detector banks, the sum covers the range $-7 \leq h, k, l \leq 7$.

The total transmission, T_{tot}^{mod} for the case of two diamonds is then the product of the two individual transmissions multiplied by an overall scale factor C.

$$T_{tot}^{mod} = C T_{UB1}^{mod} \cdot T_{UB2}^{mod}$$

A residual, χ^2 can then be defined as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_1^N (T_{tot}^{meas} - T_{tot}^{mod})^2 / (2\delta T_{tot}^{meas})^2$$

Where δT_{tot}^{meas} are the standard deviation associated with transmission measurement at each of the N ToF points at which is it measured.

The best fit is then found by minimising χ^2 with respect to the variables of the model described above. Minimisation is achieved using the FMINCON routine in the MATLAB Optimization Toolbox, which finds the minimum of a constrained nonlinear multivariable function.

Constraints

As upstream and downstream diamonds are typically closely aligned with each other (usually to within +/- 1°) and with the pseudo-LeBail approach used, it was important to pay close attention to the refinements and apply certain constraints.

Upper and lower bounds can be defined for any of the variables in refinement. Peaks are typically least broad in the lowest pressure measurements, leading to smaller problems with overlap. Thus, the low-pressure refinement is run with less stringent constraints. The best fitting parameters are then used as initial conditions for the higher pressure measurements.

One of the most important constraints is of the set of intensity multipliers. The greatest stability is found by fixing these to be the same for each of the two diamonds and only refining a single scale factor between the two of these. A better fit can be obtained by allowing independent variation of a different set of A_{hkl} for the two diamonds, but there's a risk of over-fitting, leading to non-physical dip spectra.

The Fig below shows the best fit to the low strain transmission spectrum which has $\chi^2 = 2.8$.

Figure 40 (A) shows a comparison of the total calculated pattern compared with the measured data, the residual between the two measurements is shown. The locations of dips due to the two diamonds are indicated with vertical ticks, with the upstream diamond the lower and downstream diamond upper ticks. (B) shows the contributions of each individual to the total pattern. It's clear that in this case, the upstream diamond is less well oriented to the beam than the downstream diamond. For example, the longest wavelength cluster of reflections corresponds to the four 111-type reflections that satisfy the Bragg condition (e.g. $\bar{1}11, \bar{1}\bar{1}1, \bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1}$ and $\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1}$). For an anvil where the a-axis is perfectly parallel to the beam, these would all be observed at the same wavelength.

Transforming from wavelength to d-spacing

Once the upstream transmission spectrum has been extracted from the fitting process, the final step is to convert this into a function of d-spacing, to provide a correction for the sample diffraction data. In Bragg peaks from a crystalline sample occur at specific d-spacings, for each Miller plane within the lattice, thus, the conversion to d-spacing – typically called 'focusing' - gives rise to sharp peaks in d. In contrast, the transmission spectra consists of features at fixed *wavelength* and focusing has the opposite effect of broadening out these features as each specific wavelength will sweep to different d-spacings according to diffraction angle 2θ .

When focusing the upstream transmission spectrum, it's critical to ensure that correct normalisation is observed, to maintain the appropriate averaging across the detector. Focusing was attempted by two completely independent routes. Firstly, software previously developed to calculate the (wavelength dependent) attenuation effect of the sample and gasket assembly SNAPATT was used. Secondly, intrinsic algorithms in the MANTIDPLOT software package were used to do the same averaging. The MANTIDPLOT package has the advantage that it is also used to focus the data and allows for implementation of the same pixel mask used in this process. As described previously [ACA transactions ref], single-crystal diamond spots have to be removed prior to focusing and this masking process weights the sampling of 2θ values impacting the shape of the attenuation correction.

Figure 3 compares the focused transmission spectrum from the upstream diamond for the highest pressure run 13148 for both MANTIDPLOT and SNAPATT. In the former, the full mask is applied, where as in the latter only a minimum and maximum 2θ limits are applied. The resulting corrections are very similar. The SNAPATT output is smoother because the pixel sizes employed are much larger. The systematic underestimation of the correction towards lower d in the SNAPATT function reflects slight differences in the 2θ limits used. The MANTIDPLOT correction should be more appropriate as it implements the exact limits also required by the data.

In either case, the correction has a distinct form consisting of three broad dips roughly centred on 0.8, 1.3 and 1.7 Å d-spacings. The maximum extent of the correction at this pressure would be to cause a ~15% modification of measured diffraction intensities.

Figure 41 (A) The functional form of the diamond attenuation correction in d -spacing generated by the two separate focusing programs. (B) Shows the effect of diamond orientation. Although the overall shape of the correction is similar, the downstream diamond, which has its a axis closest to parallel to the beam has sharper variation in the finer detail of the correction. In the less well aligned upstream diamond, this variation is averaged out more.

As is evident from Fig 3, the orientation of the upstream and downstream diamonds are quite different with the latter being more closely oriented to the beam. These datasets can then be used to test the effect of diamond orientation on the final attenuation correction. This is also shown in Figure 41, which compares the focused attenuation function for both upstream and downstream diamonds.

Implementation of correction

The focused attenuation correction function, generated from the fitted upstream diamond component of the total measured transmission function for a given run provides a correction to the sample diffraction intensities. As seen, this effect is a function of both upstream diamond orientation relative to the beam and the diamond mosaicity, which is modified by increasing strain. To accurately correct a diffraction dataset, it is therefore necessary to couple each diffraction measurement with a specific transmission measurement in order to provide a custom correction for each measurement.

Appendix M Budgetary analysis

INSTRUMENT BUDGET		MANPOWER	MATERIALS	R&D	Quantity	€ Unit	€ Total	€ + Contingency [40%]	TOTAL
		MANPOWER	1,628,000.00 €						12,164,460.00 €
		MATERIALS	10,409,960.00 €						10,720,710.00 €
		SERVICES	126,500.00 €						1,815,000.00 €
		R&D	660,000.00 €						1,815,000.00 €
		MANPOWER			9600	75.00 €	720,000.00 €	792,000.00 €	922,900.00 €
		MANPOWER			1600	50.00 €	80,000.00 €	88,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			400	60.00 €	24,000.00 €	26,400.00 €	
		SERVICES			10	1,500.00 €	15,000.00 €	16,500.00 €	
		MANPOWER			1600	50.00 €	80,000.00 €	86,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	20,000.00 €	20,000.00 €	22,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			170	10,000.00 €	1,700,000.00 €	1,870,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			170	5,000.00 €	850,000.00 €	925,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			170	5,000.00 €	850,000.00 €	925,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			6	1,500.00 €	9,000.00 €	9,900.00 €	
		MATERIALS			170	9,000.00 €	1,530,000.00 €	1,668,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			800	100.00 €	80,000.00 €	86,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			480	50.00 €	24,000.00 €	26,400.00 €	
		MATERIALS			2	150,000.00 €	300,000.00 €	330,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	100,000.00 €	100,000.00 €	110,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			2	150,000.00 €	300,000.00 €	330,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			4	10,000.00 €	40,000.00 €	44,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	30,000.00 €	30,000.00 €	33,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			80	100.00 €	8,000.00 €	8,800.00 €	
		MANPOWER			120	50.00 €	6,000.00 €	6,600.00 €	
		MANPOWER			1600	50.00 €	80,000.00 €	86,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	20,000.00 €	20,000.00 €	22,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			2	10,000.00 €	20,000.00 €	22,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	2,000.00 €	2,000.00 €	2,200.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	5,000.00 €	5,000.00 €	5,500.00 €	
		MANPOWER			40	100.00 €	4,000.00 €	4,400.00 €	
		MANPOWER			3200	50.00 €	160,000.00 €	176,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			3	50,000.00 €	150,000.00 €	165,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			5	10,000.00 €	50,000.00 €	55,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			3	20,000.00 €	60,000.00 €	66,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			3	10,000.00 €	30,000.00 €	33,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			1	100,000.00 €	100,000.00 €	110,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			80	100.00 €	8,000.00 €	8,800.00 €	
		MATERIALS			5	10,000.00 €	50,000.00 €	55,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			4	10,000.00 €	40,000.00 €	44,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			20	100.00 €	2,000.00 €	2,200.00 €	
		MANPOWER			1600	50.00 €	80,000.00 €	86,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	70,000.00 €	70,000.00 €	77,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	1,450,000.00 €	1,450,000.00 €	1,595,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	800,000.00 €	800,000.00 €	880,000.00 €	
		MATERIALS			1	675,000.00 €	675,000.00 €	742,500.00 €	
		MANPOWER			1	50,000.00 €	50,000.00 €	55,000.00 €	
		MANPOWER			120	100.00 €	12,000.00 €	13,200.00 €	
		MANPOWER			80	50.00 €	4,000.00 €	4,400.00 €	

Comments
Instrument base structure without detectors
10B detectors (only vav)
Scintillator detectors (only vav)
3He detectors (only vav)
See elements in the list
Physicist and mechanical engineer during 3 years
Designer during 1 year
Purchase officer 2/3 of his time during one year
40 weeks. Guide, housings, supports and shielding
m=2, 170m flight path. Costs 2014 (it may rise)
m=3. This assumes the most expensive estimation (SwissNeutrinos, SDW). Costs 2014 (it may rise)
170m flight path
Every 30m. Estimated price (not contrasted)
Lead 75mm reinforced with Steel 10mm. 170m flight path
18 weeks / 2 technicians to install the housing, align the guides and close the shielding
12 weeks. Design at ESS Lund. Adaptation of the standard design
Double-blind configuration.
Common casemate.
1 week / 2 technicians to integrate and align choppers
1 week / 2 technicians to close the shielding
2 weeks. Simple slits
One year development by a postdoc engineer
Simple jaws made of borated PEHD + Sintered BaC
solid BaC component and set of exchangeable tips
Aluminum mechanowelded plates covered by BaC
1 week / 2 technicians
2 years development by a postdoc engineer
cost per year of prototype cells, seats, avil supports
cost per cell
8 pairs diamond anvils/year for 3 years at ~€2.5k/pair. During prototyping many avil failures are inevitable.
cost per year for prototypes
Includes technical consultancy, pressure cell designing, and finite element analysis calculations
1/2 weeks / 2 technicians
1 year of a postdoc engineer
ESS detector group estimate
ESS detector group estimate
30% uncertainty in detector costing
Aluminum mechanowelded structure + Cylindrical motorised guided system
1 week / 2 technicians for the integration
1 week / 2 electronic technicians for the cabling
1 week / 1 electronics engineer for the setting up of the detector
Block of borated PEHD + BaC

